

RESPOND

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Syrian Migrants in Sweden

A Survey on Experiences of Migration and Integration

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project that aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 12 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present dataset belongs to WP7 which complements other work packages by providing quantitative data and indicators of forced migrants experiences, difficulties, attitudes, and plans, as experienced among Syrians in Sweden.

Summary

This report explores the experiences of Syrian migrants in Sweden in the areas of border crossings, refugee protection, reception, integration, and their psychological health conditions. The survey was conducted in Sweden between June 2019 and May 2020 and focuses on Syrian migrants, aged 18 years or older, arriving in Sweden in 2011 and upward. The sample of this survey study included 639 respondents and the questionnaires were filled on paper (n=464) or via a web survey (n=175), both in Arabic. The study used convenience sampling in smaller strata locations, while trying to elicit answers from a diversified group of Syrians. The geographical distribution of the questionnaires took place in five regions: Stockholm region (Stockholm 130, Södertälje 47); Malmö region (Malmö 176, Trelleborg 29, Eslöv 14); Göteborg region (Göteborg 77); Middle region cities (77); and Small region, towns, and villages (86).

The number of Syrians has dramatically increased since the start of the war in 2011, to reach 128,654 in 2020, with a peak of 51,338 asylum seekers from Syria during the so called “refugee crisis” in 2015. The 2015 refugee influx not only paved the way for a significant policy shift and legislative reforms in Swedish migration policy, but it also had an impact on the social, economic, and political spheres. The Syrian refugees are most impacted due to this policy shift as the largest share of applications for asylum came from Syrians since 2000 up until 2020, according to the Swedish Migration Agency Statistics. However, only the pre-2016 law granted respondents a permanent residency, none of the respondents (except resettlement refugees) received permanent residency after the 2016 Temporary law came into effect in Sweden.

In our sample, the vast majority of the survey respondents, almost three-fourth, had permanent residency as their current legal status, however, this was based on pre-2016 law, compared to almost a quarter with temporary residency based on 2016 Temporary law. In terms of the gender of the respondents the majority (54.8%) were male which is also in line with the official data from Statistics Sweden. The age structure ranged from 18 to 72 years and the majority of the respondents fell into the age group 40+. The sample included Syrians with different levels of education, from those who completed primary school to a university degree. Almost half of the survey participants were married and with children while one-third declared to be single. In terms of religion, the majority were Sunni Muslims in the sample. Being a Syrian and Arab/Assyrian/Palestinian/Kurd was the most common declaration in terms of culture of origin where almost half of survey respondents self-identified simply as “Syrian” and the vast majority included being Syrian in their self-identification.

The length of the journey of the participants from leaving home in Syria and till reaching Sweden ranged from 1 day to over 3 years (crossing from 1 to 12+ national borders) where the largest share (about one-third) declared that their journey lasted less than a month and for only a few, it was more than 3 years. However, whether the length of the journey was shorter or longer, the majority of participants reported encountering some sort of obstacles/difficulties during their journey to Sweden: the lack of money, smugglers, border controls, natural obstacle were the most common. The results show that there are mainly four primary sources of information about the route to Sweden among survey respondents, where more than half of the respondents relied on their friends, followed by family, smugglers, media and social media. The vast majority of the participants responded that

they did not experience any pushback while trying to enter Sweden and less than one in ten reported to face detention after leaving Syria.

Upon arrival during their first days and weeks in Sweden, more than six in ten participants received some support such as a place to stay (most mentioned), followed by food/water/clothing, information, transport and legal assistance. More than two in ten participants said that they did not need any support, however more than one in ten were not offered support despite needing it. Friends and relatives most frequently provided support upon arrival, followed by local people also serving as support givers. Participants also mentioned international and local humanitarian organizations, Police/soldiers/border guards, mosques/churches, and public institutions as support givers.

The sample presented that the majority lived in rented apartments, both among those with permanent residency and temporary residency, followed by rented single rooms. A big proportion of respondents used Swedish language classes as the only strategy for learning the language. The majority of female respondents never had a paid job in Sweden compared to almost half of the male respondents. More than one-third of the male respondents had a paid job at the time of the survey while it was less than one-fourth in case of female respondents. In terms of legal status, about half of the respondents with temporary residency compared to those with permanent residency had a paid job during the survey. Respondents' jobs in Sweden during the survey varied considerably where the largest share of respondents were working as 'unskilled worker'. Municipalities have a great difficulty providing relevant jobs, leading to many newcomers working in sectors far from their expertise.

The findings of this survey study shows that the clear majority felt safe in their neighbourhood, while a small proportion felt unsafe or somewhat unsafe. Overall, males more than females expressed feeling unsafe in different contexts and in relation to different factors, refugee neighbourhood, racism/discrimination, and bad individuals being the main explanations. In terms of experiences of discrimination, one fourth express such feelings (more so among males) in different contexts: work, education, housing, medical care, in public settings, by authorities, among others.

In terms of self-assessment of mental health, although going through difficult experiences of the war and the refugee journey, the vast majority of respondents declared their mental health to be fair, good or very good while a small proportion declared their mental health to be poor or very poor. This self-assessment of their mental health did not vary considerably across genders, however the sample showed differences for mental health across the legal statuses. Those with temporary residence permits in a larger proportion declared to have a very poor or poor mental health compared to those with permanent residency. In terms of self-evaluation of resilience, the clear majority found themselves to be 'able to adapt when changes occur' and 'bounce back after illness, injury or other hardships'. A majority responded with a strong resilience level, slightly higher for those with permanent residency than temporary and for males than females. The majority of participants marked family, faith, friends as very helpful coping factors when facing difficult situations, however, a substantial percentage also marked the same factors as not at all helpful.

The number of applications for Swedish citizenship remained at a historically high level in 2019, according to Swedish Migration Agency. The sample presented that the majority of the respondents (slightly less than eight in ten) did not have the Swedish citizenship while

about slightly more than two in ten already had it. Moreover, the vast majority of the respondents (both males and females) saw the application process of citizenship as a long and complicated legal procedure. Almost half of the respondents, never thought of leaving Sweden and going back to Syria, while almost a fifth, mentioned that they might return if the war ends and the political situation settles down there. Attitudes towards a potential return to Syria varied across genders and legal status where more females than males and more respondents with temporary residency than those with permanent residency thought returning to Syria. The overwhelming majority of the respondents (about eight in ten) never thought of settling in another country away from Sweden and Syria, and this attitude did not vary much across genders and legal status.

This survey study illustrates that the experiences of Syrian migrants in Sweden in the areas of border crossings, protection, reception, integration, and their psychological health notably vary across gender and legal status. Syrian refugees face significant difficulties not only in their home country and during their refugee journey but also upon arrival in Sweden. Although the overwhelming majority of Syrians never think of further migration from Sweden, only a few feels that they truly belong to the Swedish society. Their integration experiences are impeded primarily due to the recent restrictive migration policies, which put their future in a state of 'uncertainty', and due to the discrimination they face in different context in the host society. All forms of integration pathways need to be intensified and a more positive attitude of welcome and acceptance is needed from the host society population.

1. Introduction

This report presents selected results from a quantitative survey among adult Syrians who arrived in Sweden after 2010. The survey was part of Work Package 7 of the H2020 project *RESPOND – Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond*. The aim of the survey was to:

- map and analyse Syrians' experience in the area of border crossings, refugee protection, and reception in the host country
- study Syrian forced migrants' socio-economic and socio-cultural integration and their psychosocial health conditions
- increase our knowledge on migration and migration governance

The report presents first the methodological background to the study, including sampling, procedure, monitoring, questions, data processing, and database formatting. This is followed up by demographical background of the study population, and the study limitations. A first part of the data results is described along the experiences of the road of migration, including the journey, borders crossed, source of information for migration, pushbacks, support received upon arrival, and detention. Following this, the main result section focuses on housing conditions, language level and learning, employment conditions, psychological health and resilience, safety in neighbourhood, protection, safety, support, perceived discrimination, citizenship, belonging, and return or re-migration.

The data used for this report will be open to the public (on a CC BY 4.0 licence) under the doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4646813 after the RESPOND completion of the project. Please reference the database as: Cetrez, Ö. & Jancewicz, B. (2021). Database RESPOND Survey in Sweden. Sweden country report database. Doi: <https://zenodo.org/record/4646813#.YGM7DC9Q2gQ>.

1.1 Methodology

The survey focuses on Syrian migrants (aged 18 years or older) arriving in Sweden in 2011 and upward and was conducted in Sweden between June 2019 and May 2020. Respondents were recruited in multiple locations in Sweden, categorized broadly according to the administrative division of the Swedish municipalities (Statistiska Centralbyrån, 2010). Five regional groups were categorized: Stockholm region, Malmö region, Göteborg region, middle region (cities) and small region (villages and towns).

The official Swedish data on Syrian in Sweden are mostly about the number of refugee applications, residence permits, family reunification and granted citizenships. However, we did not find statistics on the geographic distribution of Syrian refugees in Sweden.

Only a few Syrians sought asylum in Sweden before the Syrian war started in 2011. The number of Syrians has dramatically increased since that year to reach 128,654 in 2020, with a peak in 2015 of 51,338 asylum seekers from Syria. According to the Swedish Migration Agency Statistics, the largest share of applications for asylum came from Syrians, 17 percent of all the applications received since 2000 up till 2020. The dramatic increase of Syrian refugees since 2011 played the major role in raising the number of asylum applications of Syrians to be the biggest in twenty years. (Migrationsverket, n.d)

The increase in asylum seekers who arrived in Sweden after fleeing the war, has been accompanied by an increase in the number of refugees' families who came to Sweden to reunite with their family members. According to the Swedish Migration Agency, 55,599 Syrians granted residence permits for family reunification between 2011 and 2020. (Migrationsverket, n.d)

Sample

A satisfying sampling frame for the studied population was not available, as people in Sweden are not registered by ethnicity, but only by citizenship. Thus, the study used a convenience sampling in smaller strata locations, while trying to elicit answers from a diversified group of Syrians. The interviewers recruited study participants using personal contacts, the snowball method and by asking people in public spaces to participate (such as the streets, in malls, language schools, places of worship). Respondents representing the following categories were of interest:

- Gender (male and female)
- Age difference
- Educational difference
- Refugee status with a permanent residency through UNHCR
- Legal status:
 - Refugee status with permanent/temporary residency based on the applicability of pre/post-2016 new law
 - Subsidiary Protection status with permanent/temporary residency based on the applicability of pre/post-2016 new law

- Family reunification based status with permanent/temporary residency based on the applicability of pre/post-2016 new law
- A person otherwise in need of protection status with a temporary residency permit
- Religion (e.g. Sunni, Shia, Yazidi, Druze, Christian)
- Background culture (e.g. Syrian, Kurdish, Assyrian/Syriac, Chaldean, Turkmen)
- Geographical area of residence

Respondents filled out the questionnaire by themselves either on paper or via the survey's website. These methods allowed respondents to be more comfortable when answering difficult questions and enabled the researchers to gather data swiftly. However, if someone needed assistance the interviewers were available to help and explain the questions (e.g. in the case of illiterate respondents, to read aloud the questions and write in their oral answers). In each case, respondents could decide, whether they wish to fill out the questionnaire right there and then when they met the interviewer, or whether to fill it out at home or in some other location that suits them.

Using a strata along geographical area, the result of the geographical distribution of the questionnaires represents the following five regions (see Figure 1): 1. Stockholm region (Stockholm 130, Södertälje 47), 2. Malmö region (Malmö 176, Trelleborg 29, Eslöv 14), 3. Göteborg region (Göteborg 77), 4. Middle region cities (77), and 5. Small region, towns, and villages (86). Malmö was the region with the biggest number of participants as it hosted most of the Syrians. The geographical place of Malmö made it the gate of Sweden for Syrians who came by land through Denmark. Most newcomers who arrived in Malmö settled down in it as it has many previous immigrants from Syria, Iraq or Lebanon who could help them in housing and employment. The Stockholm region came right after Malmö with 167 questionnaires collected, where most participants were located in the suburbs of the capital because of the housing possibilities.

Figure 1. Location in Sweden where the survey was conducted.

Procedure

The original questions were written in English and translated into Arabic, as all Syrians speak Arabic. The research team had competency in Arabic and with a diverse cultural background. The team had also experience in survey studies and analysis. The team together had a profound understanding of the Syrian and Swedish cultures as well as the Swedish protection regime. After several rounds of discussion and improvements of the questionnaire, it was also pilot-tested among Syrians in Sweden and when needed amended and improved. The final questionnaire was back-translated to English to check for linguistic and cultural meanings.

Once the questionnaire was ready for use, a consulting company was chosen, based on their skills and ability to perform the data gathering. With the company, the interview

techniques and ethical awareness of the research field in Sweden were discussed. The selection process and capacity building were also discussed. The interviewers were carefully selected and trained through several sessions.

Follow-up and monitoring process

For the data collection monitoring and support process, the researchers, the interviewers, and the statistical experts from the RESPOND research team in Poland collaborated. Ethical concerns in data gathering, sharing and preservation were carefully planned. With close collaboration between researchers and interviewers possible challenges from the field were handled. Fieldwork progress was discussed and documented on a weekly basis. This helped us identify missing or underrepresented groups in data collection, and when needed they were more closely targeted.

The ongoing monitoring process allowed the researchers to early react to problems with recruiting representatives of various groups and gaining access to some institutions. Some obstacles encountered were linked to respondents who were illiterate or needed an interpretation of classic or difficult Arabic sentences. The researchers advised the interviewers how to explain or clarify the questions to respondents in a neutral non-suggestive way. This happened once in Göteborg. The interview was conducted in one of the Swedish language schools for immigrants (SFI). There was one participant who had difficulties in reading the questionnaire in standard Arabic language, so the interviewer had to read every question for him in a simple Syrian dialect. Also, there was a woman who had filled the questionnaire but refused to hand it over, claiming that she changed her mind after she discussed it with her husband over the phone. In one school the headmaster was not happy that the questionnaire did not include questions concerning LGTB's rights and he refused to let the interviewers to interview the schools' students. In another language school, the headmaster did not trust that the collected data would not be used for political agenda. The interviewers were a husband and a wife and this helped a lot to gain the trust of the female participants.

Questions

Following ethical guidelines, the questionnaire included an information letter, including the aim of the study, how data would be preserved and used. They were informed that filling in the questionnaire meant giving informed consent. When interviewed face to face, this information was also given orally.

The questionnaire covered questions, relevant for Work Packages 2-5 of the RESPOND project. It included, apart from the introduction and introductory questions, questions on demographics, and metadata and feedback comments. The following four modules were covered:

- A. Journey, route and reception
- B. International protection
- C. Integration – education (including language), employment, citizenship, housing
- D. Psycho-social health and discrimination

Data entry and processing

The questionnaires were filled on paper (n=464) or via a web survey (n=175), both in Arabic. Answers given on paper were later entered into an Uppsala's University computer program. The data entry was supervised and controlled by the researchers. After the data entry, the paper questionnaires were securely archived. Later, the database was tested for completeness and consistency, and the arising doubts were cross-checked with the paper questionnaires. After data entry and review, the database was cleaned, formatted and anonymised.

The database formatting

The dataset was formatted using R and SPSS. Each variable is described by the question label and answers (if applicable) by value labels. The missing values were coded using nines e.g. 99, 999, 9999 or 99999. Filtered questions (e.g. if a respondent answered that he/she is not working they were not asked the question on how many hours do they work) were marked by 98, 998, 9998 or 99998 codes.

1.2 Data on Syrians in Sweden

1.2.1 Legal status

For many years, Sweden had one of the most liberal and generous protection and migration policy in Europe where permanent residency was the type of permit granted to protection beneficiaries in light of chapter four of the Aliens Act regardless of their legal status as a refugee or other protection based statuses (Borevi & Shakra, 2019, p 10). Nevertheless, Swedish protection policy towards Syrian asylum seekers has changed on several occasions since the eruption of Syrian war in 2011. In 2012, Sweden changed its long-term policy in providing permanent residence permits when Syrians were granted asylum in Sweden and instead gave them only a temporary residence permit. This change was attributed to the large number of Syrian asylum seekers applying for asylum in Sweden. However, this policy was changed in 2013 and a permanent residence returned to be the norm again as the Syrian conflict was assessed to be of long-term nature (Borevi & Shakra, 2019, p 12). However, following the so-called “refugee crisis” of 2015 (Shakra et al., 2018) Sweden’s migration policy changed again and took a U-turn towards more restrictive measurements. The Swedish Migration Agency described the shift as moving from the most generous asylum laws to the minimum EU level of asylum seekers protection (Swedish Migration Agency, 2020) This restrictive policy was implemented through the Act (2016:752) on Temporary Limitations to the Possibility of Being Granted a Residence Permit in Sweden, also known as the Temporary Act (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). Under this Act, individuals, who have applied for and been given asylum since July 2016, receive a temporary residence permit for either three years or thirteen months depending on which type of legal status was granted to them. Moreover, the category “others in need of protection” is entirely excluded from the Temporary Act (FARR, 2019). The only group of persons, who can still seek asylum and be granted permanent residency since the implementation of the Temporarily Act in 2016, are the so-called quota refugee through UNHCR’s resettlement program (Swedish Migration Agency, 2019). This Temporary Act was initially intended for a temporary period of only three years but was prolonged until 19th July 2021 (Barthoma et al., 2020). Restricted access to permanent legal status in Sweden not only curbs the possibility of gaining citizenship but also limits access to rights and opportunities (Cetrez et al., 2020). After July 2016, the beneficiaries of the subsidiary protection status could apply for family reunification only when complying with the maintenance requirements. This includes the applicants’ ability to provide adequate housing and to support themselves and their family members with whom they wish to be reunited with in Sweden (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020).

The changes in the Swedish asylum policy caused us to consider respondents’ legal status as one of the key factors. Overall, survey participants’ statuses were divided into eight categories depending on the type of their residence permit, the law applicable when the permit was granted and whether the permit was a result of family reunification. We divide those eight categories into two groups related to the duration of the residence permit in Sweden (whether it was either permanent or temporary). The focus of the two categories is to explore the impacts of having permanent residence in comparison to obtaining a temporary one and vice versa.

As seen in Figure 2, only the pre-2016 law granted respondents a permanent residency. None of the respondents (except resettlement refugees) received permanent residency after the 2016 temporary law¹ came into effect in Sweden, so all who arrived later were given only temporary residency. Three in ten respondents (30.0%) had refugee status with permanent residency, while one in ten respondents (10.2%) had refugee status with temporary residency. More than two in ten (20.5%) had family reunification based status with permanent residency (17.4%) and temporary residency (3.1%). Slightly less than a quarter of the sample (24.1%) had subsidiary protection status with permanent residency (15.6%) and with temporary residency (8.5%). Almost one in ten (9.2%) survey respondents had refugee status with permanent residency (UNHCR). Only a few respondents (1.6%) fell into the category of a person otherwise in need of protection with temporary residency.

Figure 2. Survey respondents by their current legal status in Sweden (in %).

Note: N = 639 (including 28 missing).

¹ Under this temporary law, everyone who applies for and is given asylum receives a temporary residence permit (except resettlement refugees), at the same time making family reunification very difficult.

Figure 3 shows the grouping of the legal statuses into permanent or temporary. More than seven in ten of the survey respondents (72.3%) had permanent residency as their current legal status, compared to almost a quarter (23.3%) with temporary residency which is mainly given based on the 2016 Temporary Law.

Figure 3. Survey respondents by their current legal status in Sweden categorized as permanent or temporary (in %).

Note: N = 639.

1.2.2 Gender

As seen in Figure 4, in terms of the gender of the respondents the majority (54.8%) were male while 45.2% of the respondents were female. The official data from Statistics Sweden also shows similar statistics where about 55.9% of the Syrian population living in Sweden are male and 44.1% are female, thus our sample reflects very well the overall population figures (Sweden Central Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Figure 4. Survey respondents by gender (in %).

Note: N = 639.

1.2.3 Age

Figure 5 mirrors the age structure of the survey respondents living in Sweden where their age ranged from 18 years to 72 years. While comparing three different age groups (as shown in Figure 6), the majority of the respondents (36.6%) fell into the category of 40+ age group, followed by the age group of 18-29 (34.9%). The age group 30 to 39 had a lower share of the respondents (28.5%) compared to the other two age groups.

Figure 5. Respondents' age.

Note: N = 639.

Figure 6. Respondents by age group (in %).

According to the official data in Sweden Central Bureau of Statistics (SCB, 2019), the proportion of men and women among refugees and their relatives in each age group was relatively evenly distributed. However, while the age group 20-24 constituted the smaller group, the age group of 25-34 constituted the larger group in Sweden.

Figure 7. Refugees and relatives age 20-64 year, by gender and age, 2018 (in %).

Source: SCB, Arbetskraftsundersökarna (AKU) and STATIV/RTB (2018)

1.2.4 Education

Figure 8 confirms that the sample includes Syrians with different levels of education (Education in Syria, 2016), from those who completed primary school to a university degree. The majority of survey participants completed either a university degree (32.1%) or secondary school (31.9%). About 6% of the participants completed primary school, 13.8% completed preparatory school, and 16.2% of the participants completed an associate degree. In general, people in Sweden undergo 19.3 years of education between the ages of 5 and 39, which is more than the OECD average of 17.2 years (OECD, 2019). In Sweden, 83% (with an average 0.5% increase since 2014) of adults 25-64 years old have completed secondary education, which is higher than the OECD average of 78% (OECD, 2019). Regarding educational attainment, Sweden ranks 19th out of 40 countries with a score 1² for gender inequality, according to OECD Better Life Index.

² A score of 1 signifies that there are equal conditions regardless of gender, the higher the score, the wider the gap.

Figure 8. Respondents' educational attainment (in %).

Note: N = 636

Table 1 shows that, in terms of educational attainment and gender, the differences between male and female were small. More male respondents completed secondary school (33.8%) and primary school (7.2%) compared to female respondents (29.6% and 4.5% respectively). The shares of female and male with tertiary degrees were almost similar (32.1% of female and 30.9% of male). None of the female respondents held a PhD degree compared to 1.1% of male respondents. In terms of an associate degree, the share of female respondents (18.5%) were higher than male respondents (14.3%). Both the male and female respondents represent a range of different educational attainments.

Table 1. Respondents' educational attainment, comparison between genders (in %).

Respondents' educational attainment	Male (%)	Female (%)
Primary school (6 years)	7.2	4.5
Preparatory School (3 years) [Lower upper secondary school]	12.6	15.3
Secondary school (3 years) [Highschool]	33.8	29.6
Associate degree (2 year program)	14.3	18.5
Tertiary	30.9	32.1
PhD	1.1	0.0
Total	99.9	100.0

Note: N = 636 (349 male and 287 female respondents).

Figure 9 derived from a report done by the Swedish Central Bureau (SCB) on refugees received by Swedish municipalities between 2016-2019. The graph shows the proportion of the refugees and their family members received in 2016 by their education level. The proportion of refugees in 2016 who had pre-secondary or post-secondary education was the same, 34 percent, while 21 percent had upper secondary education. A larger proportion of men had a registered education compared with women. Among women, 17 percent lacked information on education, while the corresponding proportion among men was 7 percent. There is also a clear difference between the sexes in terms of the proportion with post-secondary education.

Figure 9. Newly arrived refugees and their family members by level of education, by gender (total aged 20-59), year of reception 2016 (in %).

Note: Förgymnasial = Pre-secondary; Gymnasial = Post-secondary; Eftergymnasial = Upper secondary; Kvinnor = Women; Män = Men; Totalt = Total.

(SCB, 2020)

1.2.5. Marital status

Figure 10 illustrates that almost half of the survey participants were married and with children (48.1%). However, almost one in ten (8.6%) were married but without children. One-third of the respondents (33.3%) declared that they were single. About 6.2% of respondents answered that they were widowed or divorced, while 3.8% answered that they were engaged.

Figure 10. Respondents by marital status and having children (in %).

Note: N = 628.

As Table 2 shows, in terms of gender differences, female respondents were more often married and with children (57.0% of women in contrast to 40.6% of men) and male respondents were more often single (43.3% of men in contrast to 21.3% of women). One in ten female respondents (10.8%) were married but without children compared to 6.7% of male respondents.

Table 2. Respondents by marital status, having children and gender (in %).

Respondents' marital status	Male (%)	Female (%)
Engaged	4.7	2.8
Widowed or divorced	4.7	8.0
Married, no children	6.7	10.8
Single	43.3	21.3
Married, has children	40.6	57.0
Total	100.0	99.9

Note: N = 628 (342 male and 286 female respondents).

1.2.6. Religion

As shown in Figure 11, in terms of religious denomination, the majority of the survey respondents, almost six in ten self-identified to be a Sunni Muslim. Two-thirds of Syrians follow Sunni Islam, according to a 2017 poll (Contemporary Middle East Political Studies in Japan, 2017 as cited in Jancewicz, 2021). About one in ten respondents self-identified themselves to be Shia Muslim (11.4%), 10% as Orthodox Christian (Syrian, Assyrian, etc.),

6.8% Catholic (Chaldean, Syrian, etc.) and 4.8% responded that they do not belong to a denomination. A small fraction of survey respondents belonged to the Druze (2.4%), Yazidi (0.5%), and Mandaean (0.2%). About 4.9% of the respondents categorised their religious denomination as 'Other', and the majority here described it as Ismaili, spiritual, respect for all religions, Greek Orthodox, Christian, or difficult to explain.

Figure 11. Respondents by religious denomination (in %).

N=629

1.2.7. Culture of origin

Figure 12 shows that almost half of survey respondents (49.3%) self-identified simply as “Syrian”, however, overall three out of four respondents included being Syrian in their self-identification (77.3%). One in four mentioned being an “Arab” (26.9%) with “Syrian Arab” being the most common combination of two identifications. Many respondents mentioned being an Assyrian (11%), a Kurd (7.5%) or a Palestinian (5.2%), some talked also about their religion or other characteristics. Overall, being a Syrian and Arab/Assyrian/Palestinian/Kurd was the most common declaration, but respondents’ replies were quite diverse (which shows in the large number of unique answers grouped in the “Other” category).

Figure 12. Respondents by their declared culture or origin.

Note: This was an open question, and respondents' answers were cleaned e.g. 'Syrian Kurdish', 'Kurd Syrian' and 'Syrian Kurd' would all be categorized as 'Syrian Kurd'. However, 'Syrian Arab Kurd' would remain as written. Answers given by less than 5 respondents were grouped into Other. N = 629.

1.2.8. Mode of questionnaire administration

As illustrated in Figure 13, the majority of the survey respondents, more than seven in ten (72.6%), filled out the paper questionnaire while the rest of the respondents, about three in ten (27.4%), filled out the online mode of the questionnaire.

Figure 13. Respondents by the mode (online vs. paper) in which they filled out the questionnaire.

Note: N = 639

1.3. Limitations

Limitations in this study refer mainly to the design and accessibility of data registers to Syrians in Sweden. The most important limitations are:

- The results of this study cannot be generalised to Syrians in Sweden at large, as we have used a convenience sampling. However, identifying and selecting respondents along several strata, ethnic/cultural origin, religious origin, age groups etc, increases the representativeness of the results. Furthermore, we have also referred to official data when possible, to compare with our results. Still, all the results illustrate patterns and trends only among the recruited respondents.
- We have limited our sampling to five geographical locations, thus leaving out many other parts in Sweden. A limited number were recruited from northern Sweden.
- Some Syrian respondents are illiterate, especially older people and women. As a result, they would be unable to fill the questionnaire on their own. It might discourage them from taking part in the survey, despite the fact that interviewers volunteered to assist them.

2. The Road to Sweden

2.1. The length of the journey

As seen in Figure 14, the length of the journey of the survey respondents from leaving home in Syria and till reaching Sweden ranged from 1 day to over 3 years. More than one-third of the respondents (35.6%) declared that their journey to Sweden lasted less than a month (8-30 days), followed by two in ten respondents who declared 31-90 days (21.5%). Slightly more than one in ten respondents declared their length of the journey to be 2-7 days (10.8%) or 91-365 days (12.1%). For 52 respondents the length of the journey was only 1 day (8.3%) however for 56 respondents it was a prolonged period: 1-3 years and 18 respondents declared that their journey from Syria to Sweden took over 3 years (2.9%), staying a longer period of time in transit countries.

Figure 14. Respondents by the declared length of their journey from leaving home in Syria till reaching Sweden (in %).

Note: N = 629.

2.2. Number of borders crossed

National authorities with responsibilities for border management in member states are required to develop national strategies for integrated border management (IBM strategy) under Regulation (EU) 2016/1624 on the European Border and Coast Guard. The Police, the Migration Agency, the Maritime Search and Rescue (Kustbevakningen), the Maritime Services (Sjöfartsverket), Swedish Customs (Tullverket), and the Swedish Security Service (Säkerhetspolisen) established the Swedish national strategy for integrated border management (Government Office 2016, Nationell strategi för integrerad gränsförvaltning as cited in Borevi & Shakra, 2019).

Figure 15 shows that the number of national borders crossed by the survey respondents on their way to Sweden varies notably ranging from one to twelve borders. About four in ten respondents (40%) declared that they crossed 3-4 national borders (including the Swedish border) to arrive in Sweden, while almost one in ten said they crossed 2, 5, or 6 national borders. About 26% of respondents declared that they crossed 7 to 10 borders and about

2% declared crossing 1 or 11 borders as well as almost 1% who crossed 12+ national borders.

Figure 15. Respondents by the number of national borders they declared crossing on their way to Sweden (including the Swedish border). (in %).

Note. N = 624.

Figure 16 shows that three in ten respondents reported no difficulties (31.8%) in their journey to Sweden. Almost half of the respondents admitted that their journey was hindered due to lack of money (44.1%). More than one third of the respondents pointed out obstacles, such as border controls (35.5%), smugglers (36.0%), and weather or natural obstacles (30.4%).

The services provided by smugglers are not only dangerous, but also expensive (Mandic, 2017 as cited in Jancewicz, 2021); but, because of conflicts and legal barriers, it becomes essential for refugees to take those services. As a result, smugglers, border controls, and a lack of money all work parallel to hinder people's journeys (Jancewicz, 2021).

Figure 16. Respondents by obstacles/difficulties encountered during their journey to Sweden, multiple-choice (in %).

Note: Each respondent could choose multiple answers. Number of respondents = 637, number of answers = 1159.

As seen in Figure 17, there are differences between male and female in their experiences of encountering difficulties during their journey to Sweden. While more women responded they didn't experience any difficulties, they also answered more for other difficulties, including health issues, danger, theft, fraud, gangs, the responsibility for children, among others.

Figure 17. Respondents by gender and obstacles/difficulties encountered during their journey to Sweden (in %).

Note: Each respondent could choose multiple answers. Number of respondents = 637 (350 males and 287 females), number of answers = 1159.

2.3. Sources of information about the route to Sweden

Figure 18 reflects that there are mainly four primary sources of information about the route to Sweden among survey respondents. More than half of the respondents (52.9%) relied on their friends to gather information about the route to Sweden, followed by family (31.8%). The third most frequent source of information used by respondents was smugglers (29.3%) which illustrates their crucial role, followed by media and social media (23.2%). Travel agencies and other sources of information (11.0% and 6.6% respectively) were also mentioned from which survey respondents drew information about the road to Sweden.

Figure 18. Respondents by their sources of information about the route to Sweden (in %).

Note: Each respondent could choose multiple answers. Number of respondents = 632, number of answers = 988.

2.4. Pushback

As illustrated in Figure 19, the majority of the respondents (82.4%) answered that they did not experience any pushback while 17.6% of the respondents recall being pushed back from the border by authorities while trying to enter Sweden.

Figure 19. Respondents by whether they faced pushback from any authorities along the border crossing (in %).

Note. N = 618

2.5. Support - whether given upon arrival

As shown in Figure 20, the majority of the respondents (64.3%) answered that they were offered and they received some support during their first days and weeks in Sweden. However, 23.7% respondents expressed that no support was needed and more than one in ten expressed that no support was offered (12.1%).

Figure 20. Respondents by their answers on whether they needed and were offered support in their first days and weeks in Sweden (in %).

Note. N = 621

As reflected in Figure 21, in terms of gender, 61.6% of female and 66.5% of male respondents were offered support and received support during the first days and weeks in Sweden. Almost three in ten (27.8%) female respondents and two in ten (20.3%) male respondents did not need any support while 10.7% female respondents and 13.2% male respondents were not offered any support.

Figure 21. Respondents by their answers on whether they needed and were offered support in their first days and weeks in Sweden, by gender (in %).

Note. N = 621 (340 male and 281 female respondents).

2.6. Support - what type?

As seen in Figure 22, the support given to respondents during their first days and weeks was rather basic in terms of the type of support. Most respondents who received support were given a place to stay (68.2%) and means of subsistence (63.9%): e.g. food, water and clothing. About one third (34.1%) mentioned receiving support for obtaining information as well as about one fifth mentioned getting support with transport, and legal assistance (22.3% and 21.6% respectively). Shakra and Szalanska (2020:69) also indicated that the majority of interview respondents in Sweden did not seek any legal support upon arrivals. Only a few people (2%) categorized the given support as 'Other'. Sweden offers a higher quality of support in many aspects of reception, such as accommodation and material support for asylum seekers, as well as procedural standards than many other EU Member States (Barthoma et al., 2020:30).

Figure 22. Respondents who received support by the type of support given during their first days and weeks in Sweden (in %).

Note. N = 399. Each respondent could choose multiple answers. Number of answers = 846

2.7. Support givers

Respondents who mentioned getting the support also specified who provided it. Friends and relatives most frequently provided support (64.7%) with local people (17.5%) also serving as support givers. The RESPOND country report on refugee protection by Shakra and Szalanska (2020:68) also indicates the same where they write “if someone had a possibility to get support from relatives, friends or local people, the person used this opportunity, often in the first place”. The local population's support for asylum seekers cannot be underestimated (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020:68). Respondents also mentioned international (15.5%) and local (5.3%) humanitarian organizations as support givers. Since 2015, civil society organisations have played an increasingly significant role in the reception system, facilitating support where the state and municipalities were unable (Barthoma et al. 2020:86). Police/soldiers/border guards, mosques/churches, and public institutions were also mentioned and overall they helped 18.3% of those who received some support. Some respondents reported getting help from other sources (5.8%).

Figure 23. Respondents who received support by the sources of support during their first days and weeks in Sweden (in %).

Note. Each respondent could choose multiple answers. Number of respondents = 399, number of answers = 507.

2.8. Detention

As shown in Figure 24, 9.4% of the survey respondents stated that they experienced detention after leaving Syria.

Figure 24. Respondents by whether they experienced detention after leaving Syria (in %).

Note. N = 618

As shown in Table 3, the length of the detention lasted from up to 2 hours to over 720 hours (over 30 days) for the respondents. 5 respondents were detained up to 2 hours where most of the respondents (32) were detained from 3 hours to 72 hours, and 16 respondents were detained from 73 hours to 720 hours as well as 4 respondents who experienced detention over 720 hours. In Sweden, the Swedish Aliens Act formulates a guidance for

handling matters related to detention (Ch.1, section 8): “The law must be applied so that a foreigner's freedom is not limited more than is necessary in each individual case” (as cited in Borevi & Shakra, 2019).

Table 3. Respondents who were detained after leaving Syria by the length of detention (in numbers).

Hours in detention	N
up to 2 hours	5
3 to 6 hours	6
7 to 12 hours	5
13 to 24 hours	9
24 to 48 hours	9
49 to 72 hours	3
73 to 168 hours (3-7 days)	8
168 to 720 hours (7 to 30 days)	8
over 720 hours (over 30 days)	4
Total	57

Note. N=57

3. Survey Results

3.1. Housing

On average, for the year 2019, households in Sweden in general spent 19% of their gross adjusted disposable income on keeping a roof over their heads, which is in line with the OECD average of 20% (OECD, 2019). In Sweden, the average household includes 1.7 rooms (-0.0% average annual increase since 2007) per person, just below the OECD average of 1.8 rooms per person (OECD, 2019). Our results show that the majority live in rented apartments, both among those with permanent residency (57.7%) and those with temporary residency (18%), followed by rented single rooms (8.20% and 4.26% respectively). Very few had their own apartment (3.28% and 0.33% respectively).

3.2. Language

Figure 25 shows a big proportion of respondents use Swedish language classes as the only strategy for learning the language. A high percentage of females (69.9%) who learn Swedish language only in classes, while 9.6% do not go to classes and learn Swedish in daily life. Also the majority of males (52.8%) learn Swedish in classes but not in daily life.

The overall impression among our interview participants regardless of gender, based on both policies and personal experiences, is that learning Swedish is critical for labour market establishment and integration as a whole (Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 25. Respondents who declared learning Swedish by their strategies for learning, by gender (in %).

Note. N = 493. Only respondents who declared learning Swedish included; 254 male and 239 female respondents.

For adults, the two-year language introduction to Swedish is provided by the Swedish for Immigrants (SFI) which is available for all who have residence permits: both temporary or permanent residency and SFI is mandatory in order to receive financial compensation (Barthoma et al. 2020). If access to the labour market is heavily dependent on someone's ability to learn Swedish, then introductory language education (SFI) after receiving a residence permit is perhaps the most effective way of achieving this (Cetrez et al., 2020).

The patterns of strategies for learning Swedish are similar for temporary and permanent residents, while permanent residents differ in terms of having other strategies as well as using learning in daily life more frequently.

Figure 26. Respondents' strategies for learning Swedish, by temporary or permanent legal status (in %).

Note. N = 478. Only respondents who declared learning Swedish included; 356 respondents with permanent and 122 respondents with temporary residency.

3.3. Employment

The employment rate in Sweden is 76.9% (+0.2% annual average increase since 2005), where the working-age population is between 15 and 64 years old and this employment rate is higher than the 68% OECD employment average (OECD, 2019). Sweden has a score of 1 (a score of 1 signifies that there are equal conditions regardless of gender, the higher the score, the wider the gap) with respect to gender inequality within that employment rate (OECD, 2019). On average, Swedes earn USD 42 393 a year, slightly less than the OECD average of USD 43 241 and the percentage of people in Sweden that has been unemployed for one year or more is currently 1.1% (OECD, 2019).

Figure 27 shows that the majority of female respondents (65.4%) never had a paid job in Sweden compared to almost half of the male respondents (47.0%). More than one-third of the male respondents (37.2%) had a paid job at the time of the survey while it was less than one-fourth (23.3%) for female respondents.

The RESPOND country report by Cetrez et al. (2020) also portrayed a similar scenario where the majority (62%) of the participants were unemployed (of which 55% women) and slightly more than one third (36%) reported that they work to earn their own money, among which the majority being men (68%). In 2019, the unemployment rate among foreign born was 15.1% and among native born was 4.4% in Sweden (SCB, 2019).

Figure 27. Respondents by their employment status in Sweden, by gender (in %).

Note: N = 530 (347 male and 283 female respondents)

In terms of employment status, slightly more than half of the survey respondents with permanent residency (51.2%) never had a paid job in Sweden while the vast majority of the respondents with temporary residency (72.4%) never had a paid job. Figure 28 also mirrors that about half of the respondents with temporary residency compared to those with permanent residency had a paid job during the survey.

A person who still has a job after four years on a temporary residence permit can apply for a permanent residence permit if he or she can support and accommodate his or her family (AIDA, 2018).

Figure 28 shows that there is a prominent effect of the legal status on the labour market participation for the respondents. The majority of respondents (72.4%) with temporary residence permits never had a paid job in Sweden, compared with half of respondents (51.2%) who have permanent residence permits. The proportion of (33.3%) of those who have permanent residency had a paid job in Sweden at the time of the survey. While, only (17.9%) of participants who have temporary residency had paid job.

Figure 28. Respondents by their employment status in Sweden, by legal status (in %).

Note. N = 530 (459 respondents with permanent and 145 respondents with temporary residency).

Respondents' jobs in Sweden during the survey varied considerably. Figure 29 illustrates that at the time of the survey the largest share of respondents (31.1%) were working as 'unskilled worker'. Almost identical proportion of respondents were working as 'specialist' (19.2%) and 'skilled worker or craftsman' (18.7%). About one-fifth of respondents were working whether as 'office worker' (13.0%) or 'service employee or salesperson' (7.3%) and only 2.1% of the total respondents as managers/supervisors/directors.

Low-skilled workers face tremendous difficulty in integrating into the labour market. While employment in the medium and high-skilled workforce has remained stable, unemployment in the lower-skilled cohort, especially among young people, has increased (Cetrez et al., 2020). Lack of language skills, a complicated process for validating diplomas, lack of low-skill job opportunities, host society attitudes, and the general labour market situation with high youth unemployment are major challenges of finding employment (AIDA, 2018).

As shown in Figure 29 the majority of respondents who had a paid job (31.1%) worked at sectors that did not require professional skills or high experiences. Such as, waiter, kitchen help or cleaner. However, only a small proportion (2.1%) worked in sectors in which professional experiences are required such as manager, supervisor or doctor.

Figure 29. Respondents who were working at the time of the survey, by their current job in Sweden (in %).

Note. N = 193. Only respondents who were working at the time of the survey included.

Figure 30 mirrors the participants' participation in the labour market by the sectors they worked in. Majority of female respondents worked in the health and social services sector and education and translation sector (19 and 14 respectively). While, the majority of male worked in the health and social services sector and the industry and crafts sector (25 and 15 respectively). In general, according to the figure the males participation in the labour market is higher than females.

Figure 30. Respondents by the sectors in which they were working at the time of the survey (in numbers).

Note. N = 193. Only respondents who were working at the time of the survey included; 128 male and 65 female respondents.

Figure 31 depicts that respondents at the time of the survey were working in a variety of job sectors. The largest share of respondents worked in the health and social service sector (22.9%), followed by foodservice (15.1%) and education and translation (14.6%). About one in eleven respondents worked in manufacturing (8.9%) and other sectors were less common. Construction, retail, agriculture sectors were reported the least among other sectors.

Municipalities have a great difficulty providing relevant jobs, leading to many newcomers working in sectors far from their expertise, as reflected in this remark: “Six out of ten work outside their profession in Sweden” (public official, Länsstyrelsen, as cited in Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 31. Respondents who were working at the time of the survey, by the sectors in which they were working at the time of the survey (in %).

Note. N = 192. Only respondents who were working at the time of the survey included.

3.4. Psychological health

According to the OECD Better Life Index 2019, 78% of the population in general in Sweden stated that they were in good health in response to the question "How is your health in general?", which is notably higher than OECD average of 69% (OECD, 2019). In particular, 75% (with +0.2% average annual increase since 2005) of people reported their health to be "good or very good" in Sweden (OECD, 2019).

Although the difficult experience of the war and the refugee journey, the majority of respondents declared their mental health to be fair, good or very good (37.3%, 34.1%, 13.8% respectively). While 9.3% and 5.5% declared their mental health to be poor and very poor (Figure 32).

Figure 32. Respondents by their self-evaluation of their mental health (in %).

Note. N = 639

The respondents' declaration of their mental health did not vary too much across genders. Figure 33 shows convergent proportions between male and female respondents.

Figure 33. Self-evaluation of mental health, by gender (in %).

Note. N = 636 (348 male and 288 female respondents).

Figure 34 shows prominent differences for mental health across the legal status of the respondents. In general, the majority indicate good or fair for their mental health. More interesting is that those with temporary residence permits in a larger proportion declare to

have a very poor mental health compared to those with permanent residency (8.6% against 4.5%). The same goes for answering that their mental health is poor. That could be explained by the privilege of the permanent residence permit as it allows refugees for family reunification and gives a long-term feeling of safety and stability in the host country.

Figure 34. Self-evaluation of mental health, by legal status (2 levels), (in %).

Note. N = 610 (148 respondents with temporary and 462 with permanent residency).

3.4.1. Resilience

Studies on processes of resilience among non-western cultures are limited. In this respect, a culturally and contextually sensitive definition of resilience, emphasising the significance of social relations, is presented by Ungar (2008, 225) is needed:

In the context of exposure to significant adversity, whether psychological, environmental, or both, resilience is both the capacity of individuals to navigate their way to health-sustaining resources, including opportunities to experience feelings of well-being, and a condition of the individual's family, community and culture to provide these health resources and experiences in culturally meaningful ways.

Figure 35 shows one of the dimensions of resilience, the ability to adapt when changes occur. While 2.4% responded not true at all for being able to adapt when changes occur, a larger number, 11.6%, answered rarely true. Still the majority found themselves able to adapt.

Figure 35. Respondents by self-evaluation of their adaptability to change (in %).

Note. N=622

The second dimension of resilience, bouncing back after illness, injury or other hardship, as seen in Figure 36, reveals a similar pattern for those respondents who answer not true at all, 3.3%, and rarely true, 8.3%. Also here, the majority answers they are able to bounce back.

Figure 36. Respondents by self-evaluation of their resilience (in %).

Note. N = 616

The CD-RISC2 scale is a sum of respondents’ answers “I am able to adapt when changes occur” and “I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships” with answers scored: 0 – “Not true at all”; 1 – “Rarely true”; 2 – “Sometimes true”; 3 – “Often true”; 4 – “True nearly all the time”. The reliability of the scale was assessed by Vaishnavi et al. (2007) and a more detailed description of the scale can be found in the scale’s manual prepared by the scale’s creators (Davidson and Connor-Davidson, 2018).

Table 4 shows the mean level by gender, females (M = 5.2) slightly lower than males (M = 5.5). Research conducted among refugees indicates a score of 5+ as a strong resilience level. A majority, 68.6%, responded with a resilience level of 5+, slightly higher for males (71.1%) than females (65.7%). Other research shows lower resilience level among Iraqi refugees in Sweden, as well as lower resilience for females (Cetrez, et al., 2021).

Table 4. Mean, standard deviation and median of respondents' resilience score on the CD-RISC 2 items, by gender.

Gender / Resilience score:	Mean	SD	Median
Male	5.52	1.85	6
Female	5.22	1.92	5

Note. N = 616

When calculating the mean value by legal status, we see a small difference, where those with permanent residency (M = 5.39) show a higher resilience than those with temporary residency (M = 5.24).

Table 5. Mean, standard deviation and median of respondents' resilience score on the CD-RISC 2 items, by legal status.

Legal status / Resilience score:	Mean	SD	Median
Permanent residency	5.39	1.91	6
Temporary residency	5.24	1.83	6

3.4.2. Coping factors

In general, 91% of individuals in Sweden say that they have someone they can rely on in difficult times, which is slightly higher than the OECD average of 89% and Sweden ranks 17/40 for quality of support network with equal conditions in terms of gender (OECD, 2019).

The coping factors marked by the majority of participants as very helpful when facing difficult situations in life were family, faith, and friends. However, a substantial percentage also marked not at all helpful for the same factors. The other factors, being out in nature and work/school, are not at all helpful for the majority, followed by very helpful. The contrasts here are interesting and need further elaboration. In an open ended response on other coping factors, respondents mentioned: ability to speak English or other languages, strong self confidence, hope, determination, patience, earlier experience, education, reading books and media, keeping distance to racist attitudes, keeping close to people from same country of origin, legal support, life experience, economy, animals, teachers, sport, stability, Sweden as a stable society, and helping others.

Table 6. Respondents by their evaluation of how much did family, faith, being in nature, work/school helped them to cope with difficulties (in %).

Response	Family	Friends	Faith, Religion, Spirituality	Work/school	Being out in nature	Other
0 (Not relevant)	8.3%	7.2%	9.2%	7.0%	11.1%	52.1%
1 (Not at all)	16.4%	14.6%	23.9%	20.0%	20.2%	24.1%
2	2.0%	5.0%	2.8%	3.9%	4.5%	1.1%
3	1.3%	3.9%	2.7%	6.3%	3.3%	0.8%
4	3.4%	6.4%	3.1%	6.1%	7.0%	1.1%
5	4.7%	11.7%	5.9%	10.3%	10.0%	2.7%
6	3.0%	5.0%	4.2%	5.9%	6.4%	2.0%
7	2.2%	5.3%	3.6%	5.8%	5.5%	1.7%
8	4.9%	6.1%	2.5%	8.5%	3.1%	1.4%
9	3.1%	3.4%	4.7%	3.6%	3.9%	1.1%
10 (Very much)	43.8%	24.4%	30.4%	15.6%	18.0%	5.0%

3.5. Protection, Safety and Support

Respondents who have a positive perception of their neighbourhood often indicate that they feel safe there, that people are welcoming to them, and that they have a sense of proximity to other aspects of their everyday lives, such as transportation, the marketplace, education, employment and so on (Cetrez et al., 2020). In most of the cases, newcomers tend to live in neighbourhoods where they have family or at least migrant communities of similar backgrounds, and this is a choice that can be understood in the sense of 'feeling safe' (Barthoma et al., 2020). Although living around people from the same place, speaking the same language, and having largely similar religion and culture offer a "safety zone" for newcomers it distances them from other populations in society (Barthoma et al., 2020). To connect Swedes and newcomers, community building and neighbourhood activities can contribute to establish networks and address the issues of discrimination and segregation (Cetrez et al., 2020).

The RESPOND interview dataset in general, showed that a close and friendly relationship with neighbours in Sweden was experienced by 28 respondents (46%), among which the majority were men (57%) (Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 41 shows that the clear majority feel safe in their neighbourhood, while a small proportion feel unsafe or somewhat unsafe, the latter more so among males.

Figure 37. Respondents by convictions about their safety in the neighbourhood, by gender (in %).

Figure 42 shows that the age group differences for feeling safe or unsafe are very small, though the middle age group (79.2%) expresses more being safe and the youngest age group (71.1%) somewhat more being unsafe.

Figure 38. Respondents by convictions about their safety in the neighbourhood and by age group (in %).

Despite efforts of municipalities to ensure geographical dispersion of refugees, many neighbourhoods depict the image of isolation of immigrants (Cetrez et al., 2020). Some respondents have problems in urban areas because of segregation and living with other immigrants as neighbours, while others feel more comfortable and safe for the same reason (Cetrez et al., 2020). Several respondents stated that they did not know anyone in their place of residence, that they felt unsafe, isolated, and that they had no connection with society (Barthoma et al., 2020).

Overall, males more than females express feeling unsafe in different contexts and in relation to different factors, refugee neighbourhood, racism/discrimination, bad individuals being the main explanations.

Figure 39. Respondents who felt safe or unsafe in their neighbourhood in Sweden (in numbers).

Note: The question was asked only to those who declared feeling unsafe or somewhat unsafe in their neighbourhoods, out of which 52 answered the question (31 male and 20 female respondents). Respondents could choose several answers.

3.6. Discrimination

The Swedish government has set clear targets for equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities for everyone with regard to discrimination and segregation, irrespective of ethnic or cultural context (Cetrez et al., 2020).

In the Sweden country report, Cetrez et al. (2020) point towards discrimination as a major obstacle, preventing newcomers from getting a permanent job. Almost a third of the interviewed persons, the majority of whom were men, said they had experienced some form of discrimination in their workplace in Sweden (Cetrez et al., 2020: 30). Lack of compassion by caregivers, feelings of not being trusted, not receiving required medication, or being refused required care are major issues related to perceived discrimination in healthcare (Cetrez et al., 2020:65). Some respondents are also concerned that they have been discriminated against in settlements because of their nationality (Barthoma et al., 2020).

Some newcomers perceived it negatively and felt discriminated against that they were not given the same rights like Syrians as in this case: “Their high priority was the refugees

from Syria, even healthy male refugees from Syria were taken well care of compared to Afghan family. That made me feel very bad and discriminated” (Afghan man, Age group 27-50, Nr.61, as cited in Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). However, “there should be no institutionalised difference in treatment with respect to nationality” (AIDA, 2020). Some respondents from Syria also complained about the investigator's discriminatory and threatening behaviour, as in the following case: “He was speaking to the children and he scared them. He told them ‘who told you that we are going to give you residency? We will send you back to Syria’ ...” (Syrian man, Age group 27-50, Nr.15, as cited in Shakra & Szalanska, 2020).

Though the majority of respondents express they have never experienced discrimination or similar in several situations, there is at least one fourth who do express such feelings when getting a job, on the street or in public; up to one fifth or a bit less expresses that when at school, at work, getting a house, by authorities, or getting medical care; and up to one tenth when in stores/restaurants or by the police or in court.

Figure 40. Respondents by their experience of discrimination in different contexts (in %).

Note. N = 612. Only respondents who answered all of the nine questions included.

As seen in Figure 45, the experiences of discrimination in different contexts look similar focusing on females alone. However, a higher percentage of male participants _Figure 46_ express the feeling of being discriminated, especially when getting jobs or in public settings.

Figure 41. Female respondents by their experiences of discrimination in different contexts (in %).

Note. N = 276. Only female respondents who answered all nine questions included.

The experiences of discrimination in different contexts is higher focusing on males alone. We see that almost a third of the males experience discrimination in the most common situations.

Figure 42. Male respondents by their experiences of discrimination in different contexts (in %).

Note: N = 336. Only male respondents who answered all nine questions included.

Presenting the results by the lack of experiencing discrimination in different situations and by gender, the pattern is the same, where females are in majority for all situations presented here. The largest differences are found related to getting hired or a job, on the street or in public, or when getting a house.

Figure 43. Respondents by their lack of experiences of discrimination in different contexts, by gender (in %).

Note: Only respondents who answered all nine questions included. N = 612 (336 male and 276 female respondents).

3.7. Citizenship and belonging

Taking into account that only those who have permanent residence permits have the right to apply for the Swedish citizenship, the majority of the respondents, 77%, did not have the Swedish citizenship. While, about 22.5% have already had it. Moreover, the largest share of the respondents, 71.4%, see the application process of citizenship as a long and complicated procedure.

The number of applications for Swedish citizenship remained at a historically high level in 2019, according to the SMA's annual report (Cetrez et al., 2020). According to Shakra and Szalanska (2020), among the participants in their study, citizenship was the most frequently mentioned reason for choosing Sweden as an asylum destination. It can also be said that Sweden continues to have a lenient policy when it comes to awarding citizenship to those who live in Sweden permanently, especially children and minor teenagers (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). Sweden among the Nordic countries still has the least complicated set of rules for naturalisation, the most common way for newcomers of becoming citizens (Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 44. Respondents by their attitudes towards acquiring Swedish citizenship (in %).

Note. N = 636

Figure 49 shows that the 'long and complicated legal procedure' was indicated to be the biggest obstacle to get Swedish citizenship by almost three-fourth of the respondents (71.4%). According to the Swedish Migration Agency, it takes at least 36 months to get a decision on the application. Xenophobia of the Swedish society (4.6%), hostility of the Swedish government towards refugees (3.2%) were also reported to be some other obstacles to getting citizenship.

Sweden has a reputation for being one of the most welcoming countries in terms of refugees and offering an easy pathway to citizenship, but in recent years especially after 2015, its migration policy has taken a restrictive turn (Barthoma et al., 2020). Many participants expressed concerns about a lack of assistance and the difficulty in obtaining information about legal statuses/opportunities and rights from state agencies, particularly the migration agency, making them feel limited, imprisoned, or tied up as a consequence of actual or perceived circumstances of limited rights and a lack of access to citizenship (Cetrez et al., 2020). One of the recurring themes among respondents was the lack of evidence of identity and identification documents which was regarded as one of the major barriers to acquiring Swedish citizenship, especially for Afghani residents (Cetrez et al., 2020). The process of acquiring citizenship and naturalisation cannot begin without a permanent residency, which has become increasingly difficult to obtain since 2016, especially for those who are beneficiaries of international protection and Sweden, like many other European countries, is struggling with lengthy processing times for asylum and citizenship applications (Cetrez et al., 2020)

Figure 45. Respondents by the perceived obstacles of getting Swedish citizenship (in %).

Note. N = 627

As seen in Figure 50, we find small gender differences concerning obstacles to getting Swedish citizenship. The vast majority of both male (89.7%) and female (86.2%) respondents pointed towards the 'long and complicated legal procedure' as the biggest obstacle for getting Swedish citizenship.

Figure 46. Respondents by the perceived obstacles of getting Swedish citizenship, by gender (in %).

Note: N = 627 (345 male and 282 female respondents).

3.8. Belonging

Figure 51 Shows that 9.6% of the respondents feel that they are much part of the Swedish society, while the same amount, 9.7%, feel that they do not belong to the Swedish society at all. The majority state that they somewhat and very little belong to the Swedish society , 49.6%, 31.1% respectively.

The sense of belonging and feeling more or less integrated are dependent on many interacting factors such as the living situation, type of neighbourhood, the time spent in Sweden, the degree of positive or negative interaction with local Swedes, the work situation, current legal status, which all contribute to the perception and degree of belonging as well as integration (Cetrez et al., 2020). A significant factor negatively affecting sense of belonging is social isolation, which may be caused by geographical location or cultural dissonance (Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 47. Respondents by their feelings of belonging to the Swedish society (in %).

Note: N = 637

The feeling of belonging varied among genders. According to Figure 52, male respondents feel more integrated in the society than females. The proportion of feeling much part of society is smaller among females compared to males.

Figure 48. Respondents by their feelings of belonging to the Swedish society, by gender (in %).

Note. N = 637 (348 male and 289 female respondents).

Figure 53 shows very small differences in the feeling of belonging across legal status of the respondents. The majority of respondents with both temporary residency and permanent residency feel that they are very little and somewhat part of the Swedish society.

A sense of stable belonging is inextricably connected to the security of permanence, as well as the hope for and path to citizenship or equivalent status in the new country of residence (Cetrez et al., 2020). Some individuals with permanent residency describe their relationships with their Swedish neighbours as "very good", while others describe it as respectful but with an underlying mistrust, which they interpret as a form of "discrimination" based on their religion or nationality (Cetrez et al., 2020).

Figure 49. Respondents by their feelings of belonging to the Swedish society, by legal status (in %).

Note: N = 610 (462 respondents with permanent and 148 respondents with temporary residency).

3.9. Return to Syria

Figure 54 shows that almost half of Syrian refugees, 47.1%, never think of leaving Sweden and go back to Syria, while almost a fifth, 17.5%, mentioned that they may return to their country of origin if the war ends and the political situation settles down there. A small group of respondents, 1.9%, state that they may return to Syria even if the war continues.

Those who require protection should quickly integrate into their new society, while those lacking such reasons should return to their home country (Regeringen, 2019 a, p. 17 as cited in Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). In fact, the Swedish Migration Agency was one of the first national migration agencies in the EU to review Syria's security situation and issue a new guideline that would allow certain Syrian asylum seekers to return to assessed safe areas in Syria (SMA, 2019 as cited in Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). With the restrictive policies of the Swedish Government introduced at the end of 2015 and early 2016, feelings of uncertainty and fear of deportation among refugees increased and the general feeling of being 'welcomed' was particularly impacted (Barthoma et al., 2020).

Figure 50. Respondents by their attitudes toward a potential return to Syria (in %).

Note: N = 639

The respondents' attitudes toward returning to Syria varies across genders. Figure 55 shows that males constitute the majority of those who never think of returning to Syria with a proportion of 51.6%, compared to 41.7% of females, while females more than males are uncertain.

Figure 51. Respondents by their attitudes toward a potential return to Syria, by gender (in %).

Note: N = 639 (350 male and 289 female respondents).

Figure 56 shows a similar pattern by attitude towards returning to Syria across legal status. There is a larger proportion among those with temporary residency who are uncertain.

Figure 52. Respondents by their attitudes toward a potential return to Syria, by legal status (in %).

Note: N = 611 (462 respondents with permanent and 149 respondents with temporary residency).

The most common regions of origin for individuals receiving return decisions were Eastern Europe and the Balkans in the early 2000s, not least Serbia, while in the last ten

years the Middle East, notably Iraq and Afghanistan, have dominated (Delmi, 2020). Looking at the period examined, 1999-2018 (Figure 57), less than half, about 44 percent, of all return cases resulted in voluntary return. Nearly a third have absconded and about 15 percent have been handed over to the Police for forced departure. An important observation from the report is that the Migration Agency's and the Police's statistics are not fully compatible, which makes both implementation and estimation of target fulfilment difficult (Delmi, 2020, p3).

Figure 53. Proportion of returning cases decided between 1999-2018 (in %).

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3. 10. Further migration

Figure 58 shows that the overwhelming majority of the respondents, 81.9%, never think of settling in another country away from Sweden and Syria. While 3.9% and 7.4% respectively consider leaving Sweden if they find job opportunities or if they get the chance to leave.

Some asylum seekers who were frustrated by the lengthy asylum process or who thought they had a poor asylum interview migrated to another country even before receiving

the SMA's decision in their cases (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020). The differential application of the Internal Flight Assessment (IFA) in France compared to Sweden and Germany, as well as the different security evaluation in Afghanistan, have resulted in the migration of thousands of Afghani young asylum seekers with rejections from Sweden to France (Shakra & Szalanska, 2020).

Figure 54. Respondents by their attitudes towards moving and settling away from Sweden and Syria (in %).

Note: N = 635.

As figure 59 illustrates, the proportions of respondents by their attitude towards settling in another country away from Sweden and Syria doesn't not vary much across gender.

Figure 55. Respondents by their attitudes towards moving and settling away from Sweden and Syria, by gender (in %).

Note: N = 635 (347 male and 288 female respondents).

Identical proportions of respondents are shown in figure 60. Refugees' attitude towards moving out of Sweden did not vary across legal status. Whether the respondents with temporary residence permits or those with permanent residence permits, both had similar attitudes regarding moving out from Sweden.

Figure 56. Respondents by their attitudes towards moving and settling away from Sweden and Syria, by legal status (in %).

Note: N = 608 (461 respondents with permanent and 147 respondents with temporary residency).

4. Conclusions

Despite its limitations, the results of this study give a valuable picture of those Syrians who have been able to settle in Sweden. For many Syrians their odyssey was a long endeavour, crossing many borders to reach their destination, experiencing long detention time, and facing many hard and different obstacles along the journey. However, the problems do not decrease once people have arrived in Sweden. Unfortunately, many unemployment continues to be a big problem and perceived discrimination is expressed in many situations, most chokingly by authorities and societal institutions that are supposed to represent safety and trust in society.

The study was successful in recruiting a diverse set of population characteristics, though not equal, including gender, legal status, age distribution, geographical location, education, marital status, religious belonging, and culture of origin.

4.1. Differences along gender and legal status

This has been an explorative survey study, thus the data has mainly been analysed descriptively, with the additional analysis by gender and legal status as independent variables. These two factors were considered important for the migration and integration debate, why the main differences for these two variables are presented here:

Gender differences:

- Females expressed fewer difficulties in general along the way to Sweden.
- Both males and females learn Swedish in language classes, however, a larger proportion of males also learn Swedish in daily life.
- Both among males and females those who never had a paid job in Sweden constitute a majority, however, among males, those who have had a paid job constitute a large proportion.
- More males were working at the time of the survey, still females were equal in number working with the education and translation sector, and more in number working in household services.
- Interestingly the mental health condition didn't differ much between men and women.
- Females express a lower resilience level than males, which is in line with previous research.
- More males than females express they feel unsafe in their neighbourhood.
- Though more males than females responded to feeling unsafe in their neighbourhood, the females stick out in numbers who express problems with local Swedes, fear of being deported, and fear from other ethnic/religious groups.
- A large proportion of males express experience of discrimination, being prevented of doing something, being harassed, or made to feel inferior, mainly so when getting

hired or getting a job, on the street or in public, at school, at work, or when getting a house.

- Though the majority feel a belonging to the Swedish society, males more than females respond much.
- Males more than females express they will never return to Syria, while females in a larger proportion are uncertain.

Legal status differences:

- While it is more characteristic for both those with temporary and permanent status to learn Swedish in language classes, those with permanent status also stand out in learning in daily life. Additionally, more respondents with permanent status learn Swedish in daily life.
- Concerning a paid job, a larger proportion among those with permanent status than those with temporary status has had a paid job. Still, the majority of both groups have never had a paid job in Sweden.
- Those with temporary residency describe their mental health condition worse than those with permanent residency.
- Those with temporary residency express a lower resilience level than those with permanent residency.
- Those with temporary residency more than permanent residency express uncertainty about returning to Syria.

4.2. Policy and programme recommendations

- When forming and developing integration policies and programmes, these should be sensitive both to gender differences and differences for those of different legal status.
- Not only refugees' experiences before migration, but also their experiences of obstacles and discrimination after resettlement, in host society, are determinants of risk that needs to be considered and addressed in most societal contexts and levels.
- Authorities and key societal institutions need to address the lack of trust perceived among refugees as well as the unmet needs of safety.
- As the majority of refugees are determined to stay in Sweden, all forms of integration pathways need to be intensified and a more positive attitude of welcome and acceptance is needed from the host society population.
- Permanent residency is beneficial for refugees in many aspects, not the least for their motivation to learn and work, as well as for their health and resilience, which will in the long run also be more beneficial for society at large.

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Appendices

Survey locations and their categorization

Location category	Location	Questionnaires	Total
Stockholm region	Stockholm	130	177
	Södertälje	47	
Malmö region	Malmö	176	219
	Eslöv	14	
	Trelleborg	29	
Göteborg region	Goteborg	77	77
Middle region (Cities)	Uppsala	13	77
	Eskilstuna	15	
	Umeå	3	
	Västeras	1	
	Växjö	1	
	Örebro	7	
	Jönköping	22	
	Kalmar	1	
	Karlstad	1	
	Trollhättan	12	
	Borås	1	
Small Region (Villages and towns)	Ronneby	3	86
	Åre	1	
	Arvika	4	
	Bengtsfors	2	
	Bodafors	1	
	Dals-Ed	7	

	Härnösand	1	
	Hultsfred	1	
	Järpen	17	
	Oskarshamn	1	
	Sävsjö	1	
	Tomelilla	1	
	Vänersborg	2	
	Vargön	3	
	Vetlanda	1	
	Bollnäs	10	
	Eksjö	6	
	Hallsberg	15	
	Nässjö	7	
	Norrköping	1	
	Örnsköldsvik	1	
	Uddevalla	3	

The questionnaire in English and Arabic

The English version is the original, from which a translation to Arabic was made. The questionnaire was later annotated by the statistician who prepared the database for sharing. Both the paper and the electronic versions, English and Arabic, are provided in appendix.

Horizon 2020

RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Migration and Beyond (770564)

Introduction

The general aim of this study is to get an understanding of the present situation of asylum seekers in recent migration. We want to ensure that information obtained from you is handled with care and will be used only in scientific publications. We are not asking for any personal information. We would be grateful if you would like to answer the questions asked. At any time, you may refuse to answer the given question. It's better to refuse to answer than give a false answer.

Please answer the following questions in regular succession. If there is any instruction in the reply line, follow the instruction.

INTRODDUCTION QUESTIONS	
S1. What is your sex/gender?	1. Man 2. Woman
S2. What is your age?	_ _ _ <i>If you are under 18, do not complete the questionnaire.</i>
S3. When did you leave Syria?	1. Year _ _ _ _ _ _ 2. Month _ _ _
S4. In which country are you currently living in? <i>If other than Sweden, do not complete the questionnaire.</i>
S5. What year did you arrive in Sweden?	_ _ _ _ _ _

Part A: JOURNEY, ROUTE AND RECEPTION	
<i>At the beginning, we would like to ask you some questions on your journey to Sweden and your experiences just after crossing the Syrian border.</i>	
A1. How long was your journey from the time you left your home in Syria till you reached Sweden? <i>Please include also the time you spent on moving within Syria.</i>	_ _ _ _ _ days
A1a_S. How many national borders did you cross before arriving in Sweden? [This question was cleaned to always include the Swedish border as well. This question was unique to the Swedish questionnaire]	_ _ _
A1b_S. Please enlist national borders that you crossed before arriving in Sweden from Syria. [question unique to the Swedish questionnaire]	1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6.

<p>A2. What were the obstacles/difficulties on your journey to Sweden?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other” answer]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weather and natural obstacles 2. Money 3. Border controls 4. Smugglers 5. Other (please briefly specify)[in the database as a2_6] 6. I have not faced any difficulties [in the database as a2_5]
<p>A3. Where did you get information about the route/journey from?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other”</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Friends 2. Family 3. Media and Social Media 4. Smugglers 5. Travel agency 6. Other (please briefly specify)
<p>A4. Where did you enter Sweden?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At land border crossing point 2. At port 3. On airport 4. Other (please briefly specify)
<p>A5. Who was trying to prevent you from entering Sweden?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other” answer]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Police 2. Border guards 3. Army 4. Coast guard 5. FRONTEX 6. Local people 7. Other (please briefly specify) [in the database as a5_8] 8. None of them, I was welcomed. [in the database as a5_7]
<p>A6. Did any authorities along the border crossings try to push you back to the country where you had arrived from?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes → go to A6a_S 2. No → go to A7 [coded as 0 in the database]
<p>A6a_S. If yes, please list in which countries. [question unique to the Swedish questionnaire]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6.

Now, please think of the first days and weeks after crossing the Syrian border.

<p>A7. What kind of support were you offered?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other”</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A shelter (a place to stay) 2. Means of subsistence (food/water, clothing etc.) 3. Logistic support to reach your destination such as the camp, relatives, or elsewhere 4. Legal assistance about your status 5. Information 6. Others (please briefly specify)[in the database as a7_8] 7. No support was offered → go to A9 [in the database as a7_6] 8. No support was needed → go to A9 [in the database as a7_7]
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<p>A8. Once you passed the Syrian border who were the first people, or institution/NGO/aid-worker that offered support?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other” answer]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local individuals 2. Relatives or friends of yours 3. Police/soldiers/border guards 4. Public institutions 5. Local humanitarian organizations 6. International humanitarian organizations 7. Mosques/ churches 8. Other (please briefly specify)
<p>A9. Did you experience detention after you had left Syria?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes → go to A9a 2. No → go to B1 [coded as 0 in the database]
<p>A9a. For how long?</p>	<p> __ __ __ hours</p>

Part B: INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION

Now we would like to ask you some questions on the protection of asylum seekers and refugees as well as on your daily life in Sweden.

<p>B1. How do you feel in your neighbourhood in Sweden?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Safe → go to B3 2. Somewhat safe → go to B3 3. Somewhat unsafe → go to B2 4. Unsafe → go to B2
<p>B2. If you don't feel safe, why?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other” answer]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Racism/discrimination 2. Problems with Swedish locals 3. Theft 4. Some bad individuals 5. Refugee neighbourhoods are unsafe 6. Sweden is not safe 7. Threats of violence/verbal assault 8. Lack of proper shelter 9. Fear of closing the shelter or camp 10. Fear of being deported 11. Fear of other ethnic/religious groups 12. Other (please briefly specify).....
<p>B3. Have you ever been ... in Sweden?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p> <p>[coded as multiple variables (one for each answer with a 0 – “No” for not chosen answers and 1 – “Yes” for chosen ones), and a separate character variable for specification of the “Other” answer]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raided/ searched 2. Insulted 3. Harassed 4. Beaten 5. Blackmailed 6. Extorted 7. Arrested/Detained 8. Evicted 9. Received departure order 10. Deported out of Sweden 11. Exposed to another kind of violence (what kind?) 12. None of the above-mentioned

B4_S.	Below you can find a list of issues related to the protection situation of refugees. For each one, please mark if it is a serious problem, a minor problem, or no problem at all for you and your family in Sweden.	Serious problem	A minor problem	No problem	Not relevant
1.	Access to labour market/ availability of jobs	1	2	3	0
2.	Access to medical care	1	2	3	0
3.	Access to education	1	2	3	0
4.	Access to adequate housing	1	2	3	0
5.	Access to residence permit	1	2	3	0
6.	Access to legal aid	1	2	3	0
7.	Access to security forces or court case when you encounter problems	1	2	3	0
8.	Protection against discrimination	1	2	3	0
9.	Protection against violence	1	2	3	0
10.	Protection against exploitation in work place	1	2	3	0
11.	Lack of safety	1	2	3	0
12.	Preconceptions and misconceptions about refugees	1	2	3	0
13.	Protection from forced relocation, expulsion, detention	1	2	3	0

[The Turkish questionnaire had additional 14th sub question here about "The requirement for 'travel permit' for within country movements"]

[The Turkish questionnaire had additional two questions here: B5 "Have you benefited from protection assistance and programmes in the last three years?" and B5a_T "Please indicate from which institutions you have received protection assistance."]

Part C: INTEGRATION – LANGUAGE, EMPLOYMENT, CITIZENSHIP							
Now we want to ask you some questions on languages that you speak and learn, your employment and citizenship.							
C1.	What level of the following languages do you have?	No proficiency	Basic communication skills/ working knowledge	Good command/ good working knowledge	Very good command	Excellent command/ highly proficient in spoken and written	Near-native / fluent
1.	Swedish	0	1	2	3	4	5
2.	English	0	1	2	3	4	5
3.	Arabic	0	1	2	3	4	5
4.	First other (<i>please specify</i>).....	0	1	2	3	4	5
5.	Second other (<i>please specify</i>).....	0	1	2	3	4	5
6.	Third other (<i>please specify</i>).....	0	1	2	3	4	5
C2.	Are you currently learning Swedish?	1. Yes → go to C3 2. No → go to C4 [coded as 0 in the database]					

C3. How are you learning the Swedish language? <u>You can select multiple answers from the list.</u>	1. Daily life in the host country → go to C6 2. Language classes in the host country → go to C6 3. Another way (please briefly specify)..... → go to C6
--	---

C4. Do you wish to learn Swedish?	1. Yes → go to C6 2. No → go to C5 [coded as 0 in the database]
C5. If you don't want to learn Swedish, please indicate why. <u>You can select multiple answers from the list.</u>	1. I don't find it necessary 2. It's too difficult 3. Other reasons (please specify)

Now we would like to ask you some questions on your job.

C6. Have you ever had a paid job in Sweden, either as an employee or as self-employed ?	1. Yes → go to C7 2. No → go to C15
C7. How long did it take you to start working after your arrival in Sweden?	__ __ __ months
C8. Are you currently working?	1. Yes → go to C10 2. No → go to C9 [coded as 0 in the database]
C9. If you are not working now, for how long were you being unemployed?	__ __ __ months → go to C15
C10. What is your current job performed in Sweden?	1. Unskilled worker (e.g. maid, waiter, kitchen help, agricultural worker, cleaner, babysitter) 2. Skilled worker or craftsman (e.g. welder, machine operator, qualified bricklayer, tailor, nurse, operator of agricultural machinery, forester) 3. Service employee or salesperson (hairstylist, beautician, cook) 4. Office worker, a technician and other middle personnel (secretary, electrician) 5. Specialist (lawyer, doctor, bookkeeper, lecturer, IT specialist, teacher, translator) 6. Manager/supervisor/director 7. Other (please specify)
C11. In which sector is your current job performed in Sweden?	1. Agriculture 2. Manufacturing (industry and crafts) 3. Retail/ wholesale trade 4. Tourism 5. Foodservice 6. Construction and renovation services 7. Household services 8. Education and translation 9. Health and social service 10. IT/banking/accounting/consulting/marketing 11. Other (please specify)
C12. How did you find your current job?	1. Through family or friends in Sweden 2. Through NGO in Sweden 3. Through official institution (e.g. Job center " Arbetsförmedlingen) in Sweden [the Turkish questionnaire has a different example here] 4. Through intermediaries 5. Another way (how?)
C13. How many hours per week do you work currently?	__ __ hours weekly
C14. What level of Swedish is required for your	0. No proficiency

<p>current job?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Only basic communication skills 2. Good command/ good working knowledge 3. Very good command 4. Excellent command/ highly proficient in spoken and written 5. Near native/ fluent
<p>C15. Have you attended any vocational training in Sweden (excluding language classes)?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes 2. No [coded as 0 in the database]
<p>C16. Based on your experience, what are the difficulties as asylum seekers/refugees when looking for a job?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Legal barrier to take up jobs officially 2. Employers not willing to hire asylum seekers / refugees 3./__ Employers not willing to pay for SGK/insurance [The paper version of the questionnaire did not contain this answer, thus this question is removed from the data] 4./3. Necessity to know Swedish language well 5./4. Only simple and low paid jobs accessible for asylum seekers / refugees 6./5. Lack of recognition of competences from home country 7./8. Other (what?) 8./9. No difficulties/ Not relevant
<p>Now we would like to ask you some questions on your citizenship and your plans.</p>	
<p>C17_S. What is your current legal status in Sweden?</p> <p>[The questions about legal status are different in Turkey and Sweden]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Refugee status (with permanent residency through UNHCR) 2. Refugee status (with permanent residency through the applicable old law before 2016) 3. Refugee status (with temporary residency through the applicable new law after 2016) 4. Subsidiary Protection status (with permanent residency through the applicable law before 2016) 5. Subsidiary Protection Status(with temporary residency through the applicable law after 2016) 6. Family reunification based status (with permanent residency through the applicable old law after 2016) 7. Family reunification based status (temporary residency through the applicable new law after 2016) 8. a person otherwise in need of protection status for example because of natural disaster or armed conflicts (with temporary residency permit) 9. Other (please briefly specify):.....
<p>C18. What is your attitude towards acquiring Swedish citizenship?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I don't want to have it 2. I would like to have it, but I don't think it's possible 3. I would like to have it and I have already applied for it 4. I would like to have it and I will apply for it in the future 5. I already have it
<p>C19. What are, according to you, the biggest obstacles in getting the host country citizenship?</p> <p><i>You can select multiple answers from the list.</i></p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Long and complicated legal procedures 2. Hostility of the host country government towards refugees 3. Xenophobia of the host country society 4. Other (please briefly specify)
<p>C20. How much do you feel part of the Swedish society?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not at all 2. Very little 3. Somewhat 4. Much
<p>C21. Which statements below may express your considerations about returning to Syria?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I never think of returning to Syria 2. I may return in case the war in Syria ends and a good government is established 3. I may return in case the war in Syria ends, even if there is not yet a good government established 4. I may return even if the war in Syria continues 5. I do not have an idea, I do not know

8.	From the police or in the courts	0	1	2	3
9.	From other authorities (e.g., Social Services, Migration office, Tax authority, National Insurance Agency)	0	1	2	3
10.	Because of Swedish language in your context outside home [This sub question is unique to the Swedish questionnaire]	0	1	2	3
11.					

D6. To what extent here in Sweden do the following help you in coping with any difficult situation you are facing? <i>Where "0" means "not relevant", "1" means not at all and "10" means very much</i>											
	Not at all									Very much	Not relevant
1. Family	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0
2. Friends	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0
3. Faith/ Religion/ Spirituality	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0
4. Work /school	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0
5. Being out in Nature (e.g. by the sea, in the wood, at the park)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0
Please add to the list any important aspects that you find in Sweden.											
6. Other (please briefly specify)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0

Parents' and Children's Rights and Integration [this whole section is unique to the Swedish questionnaire]

Statements in this section are about your attitude towards the Swedish values regarding gender equality, parental responsibility and child's rights in the Swedish law. To what extent do you agree with the following statement even if you do not have children at this time.

IN THE CASE OF DIVORCE AND ABSENT DISAGREEMENT REGARDING PARENTAL RIGHTS, THE SWEDISH SECULAR LEGAL AND JUDICIAL FAMILIAL SYSTEM STRONGLY PRE-ASSUMES THE FOLLOWING:

JOINT EQUAL PARENTAL RESPONSIBILITY IN ALL IMPORTANT DECISIONS CONCERNING THE CHILD'S UPBRINGING, EDUCATION AND WELFARE, FINANCIAL MATTERS CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTERESTS OF THE CHILD.

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
1. The Swedish system fits me well in Sweden.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

IN THE CASE OF DIVORCE AND ABSENT DISAGREEMENT REGARDING PARENTAL RIGHTS, THE SYRIAN RELIGION-BASED LEGAL AND JUDICIAL FAMILIAL SYSTEM STRONGLY PRE-ASSUMES THE FOLLOWING:

THE FATHER'S SOLE GUARDIANSHIP IN MOST SUBSTANTIAL MATTERS CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTEREST OF THE MUSLIM CHILD.

THE MOTHER'S GUARDIANSHIP UNTIL A CERTAIN AGE (13 GIRLS AND 15 BOYS) CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTEREST OF THE MUSLIM CHILD.

THE PARENTS' RELIGIOUS BACKGROUND PLAYS A CENTRAL ROLE IN RELATION TO PARENTS'- AND CHILD RIGHTS AFTER DIVORCE, WHICH MEANS

DIFFERENT RULES MAY APPLY IF THE CHILD IS SYRIAN CHRISTIAN.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
2. A. This system can work only in a Muslim country like Syria.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
2. B. This system fits me well in Syria.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
3. I am prepared to accept that a mother can have sole guardianship or custody if that is in the child's best interest.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

When it is necessary to place the child under care, due to serious shortcomings in parental care:	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
4.A. I accept that the child is placed in the care of a <u>suitable family relative</u> in Sweden if that is in the child's best interest.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
4.B. I accept that the child is placed in the care of a <u>suitable non-relative</u> in Sweden if <u>there is no suitable family relative</u> and that is in the child's best interest.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

How much would you like your children to integrate into Swedish society valuing gender equality e.g. as regards their right to develop as autonomous individuals, the right to have a boyfriend / girlfriend?	Not at all	Very little	Somewhat	Much	Completely
5.A. How much would you like it in the case of your sons?	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
5.B. How much would you like it in the case of your daughters?	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

To what extent do you agree with the following statements in relation to your children's integration into the Swedish society?	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
6.A. We have a plan to return to the country of origin	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.B. I do not care about the value base of gender equality in the Swedish society when it comes to my child's rights to choose a partner (boyfriend or girlfriend).	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.C. I wish that my children will cherish the Syrian culture values.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.D. I wish that my children will cherish the Swedish culture values.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.E. I wish my children to have a good future in Sweden.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.F. Other reasons. Please specify:.....	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?	Completely disagree	Mostly disagree	Partly agree	Mostly agree	Completely agree
7. I am ready to make some compromises concerning my religious practices to better integrate into the Swedish society.	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

In the Swedish public school system, teaching and education are non-confessional. Teaching about all the major religions is a part of the curriculum for all students. The Swedish system permits to date that faith communities operate religious schools, upon special public authorisation, for Muslim, Christian and Jewish followers. Religious or confessional elements are allowed in these educational contexts but not in the teaching, and students have the freedom to attend or not.

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?	Agree Totally	Agree Partly	Reject partly	Reject Totally	Neither agree nor reject/ I not know
8. Religious schools counteract integration	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>

DEMOGRAPHICS	
P1. What is your current relationship situation?	1. Married 2. Divorced 3. Engaged 4. Widowed 5. Single
P2. Do you have children?	1. Yes → go to P2a and P2b 2. No → go to P3 [coded as 0 in the database]
P2a. If yes, how many are with you now?	__ __
P2b. And how many are living somewhere else?	__ __
P3. Which is Your or Your parents' background culture (culture of origin)? For example Syrian, Arabic, Kurdish, Assyrian/Syriac, Chaldean, Turkoman, or other?
P4. Do you belong to a religion or religious denomination?	1. Catholic (Chaldean/Syrian/etc.) 2. Druze 3. Mandaean 4. Muslim (Shia) 5. Muslim (Sunni) 6. Orthodox (Syrian/Assyrian/etc.) 7. Yazidi 8. Other (write which one): 9. Do not belong to a denomination
P5. How religious do you feel you are?	1. Not at all 2. Very little 3. Somewhat 4. Much

<p>P6. What is the highest level of your education? [The question cafeteria is suited to Syrian respondents, but in the database these answers are renamed to be in line with the international categorizations and naming conventions: Primary school (6 years); Preparatory School (3 years); Secondary school (3 years); Associate degree (2 year program, önlisans); Tertiary; PhD]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Primary school 2. Lower upper secondary school 3. High school 4. 2 years university, -önlisans-associate degree 5. Tertiary (University) 6. PhD
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<p>P7. What is the subject area of your highest level of education? [many respondents chose the answer "Other" and gave an answer that fell within one of the categories offered – these answers were recoded appropriately]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General programmes without any subject area 2. Education and pedagogy 3. Humanities (e.g. linguistics, history, theology) and art 4. Social sciences (e.g. sociology, psychology, anthropology) 5. Economy, business and financial studies 6. Law 7. Life sciences (e.g. biology, botany, zoology, microbiology, physiology, biochemistry) 8. Physical and environmental sciences 9. Mathematics and computing 10. Engineering and technology 11. Manufacturing and processing 12. Architecture and building 13. Agriculture, forestry, fishery 14. Veterinary 15. Health and medicine 16. Social services 17. Services 18. Media, culture, tourism 19. Public administration 20. Uniformed services 21. Other (<i>please specify</i>)
--	---

<p>P8. What is the type of your current place of residence? [The interviewers did not ask about the name of the place of residence and did not verify its size, thus these are respondents' evaluations.]</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rural area 2. Small town up to 20.000 people 3. Medium town of more than 20.001 up to 100.000 people 4. Big town of more than 100.001 up to 1.000.000 people 5. Large city of more than 1.000.000 people
---	---

<p>P9_S. What type of accommodation do you have?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rented single room 2. Rented apartment 3. Own apartment 4. Rented house
---	---

	5. Own house 6. Unfinished or uncompleted shelter 7. Temporary shelter exchanged among refugees [this was “Makeshift shelter” in the Turkish survey] 8. A home that consists of several rooms [this was a “Gecekondu house” in the Turkish survey] 9. Collective Shelter or refugee camp 10. Other (<i>please specify</i>)
--	---

It was the last question. Thank you for your time.

Comments:.....
.....

Date, when the questionnaire was filled in: [the variable **interview_date** in the database]

|__|__| day |__|__| month |__|__|__|__|year

Time: [absent from the database] Start: |__|__| hour |__|__| minutes

Finish: |__|__| hour |__|__| minutes

Place, where the questionnaire was filled in (e.g. private house, coffee shop):
[absent from the database]

Village/town, where the questionnaire was filled in: [in
the database this is the variable **location**]

|__|__|__|__| Number of the interviewer (*filled out by the interviewer*) [absent from the database]

RESPOND Survey in Sweden

Introduction

The general aim of this study is to get an understanding of the present situation of asylum seekers in recent migration. We want to ensure that information obtained from you is handled with care and will be used only in scientific publications. We are not asking for any personal information. We would be grateful if you would like to answer the questions asked. At any time, you may refuse to answer the given question. It's better to refuse to answer than give a false answer.

Please answer the following questions in regular succession. If there is any instruction in the reply line, follow the instruction.

ID (name of your contact person)

Date, when the questionnaire was filled in (DD/MM/YYYY):

S1. What is your sex/gender?

- Man
 Woman

S2. What is your age? Please write it in number

S3. When did you leave Syria?

Year
Month

S4. In which country are you currently living in?

- Sweden
 Other

S5. What year did you arrive in Sweden?

Part A: Journey, route and reception

At the beginning, we would like to ask you some questions on your journey to Sweden and your experiences just after crossing the Syrian border.

A1. How long was your journey from the time you left your home in Syria till you reached Sweden? Please include also the time you spent on moving within Syria.

Days

A1a_S. How many national borders did you cross before arriving in Sweden?

A1b_S. Please enlist national borders that you crossed before arriving in Sweden from Syria.

- Lebanon
 Turkey
 Greece
 Macedonia
 Serbia
 Hungary
 Austria
 Germany
 Denmark
 France
 Italy
 Romania
 Ukraine
 Egypt
 Libya
 Bulgaria
 The UK
 Poland
 Russia
 Finland

Please enlist if you crossed other countries

A2. What were the obstacles/difficulties on your journey to Sweden? (multiple choice possible)

- Weather and natural obstacles
- Money
- Border controls
- Smugglers
- I have not faced any difficulties
- If other, please specify

A3. Where did you get information about the route/ journey from? (multiple choice possible)

- Friends
- Family
- Media and Social Media
- Smugglers
- Travel agency
- If other, please specify

A4. Where did you enter Sweden?

- At land border crossing point
- At port
- On airport
- If other, please specify

A5. Who was trying to prevent you from entering Sweden? (multiple choice possible)

- Police
- Border guards
- Army
- Coast guard
- FRONTEX
- Local people
- None of them, I was welcome
- If other, please specify

A6. Did any authorities along the border crossings try to push you back to the country where you had arrived from?

- 1. Yes go to A6a_S
- 2. No go to A7

A6a_S. If yes, please enlist in which countries.

- Lebanon
- Turkey
- Greece
- Macedonia
- Serbia
- Hungary
- Austria
- Germany
- Denmark
- France
- Italy
- Romania
- Ukraine
- Egypt
- Libya
- Bulgaria
- The UK
- Poland
- Russia
- Finland
- If other, please specify

Now, please think of the first days and weeks after crossing the Syrian border.

A7. What kind of support were you offered? (multiple choice possible)

- A shelter (a place to stay)
- Means of subsistence (food/ water, clothing etc.)
- Logistic support to reach your destination such as the camp, relatives or elsewhere
- Legal assistance about you status
- Information
- No support was offered go to A9
- No support was needed go to A9
- If other, please specify

A8. Once you passed the Syrian border who were the first people, or institution/NGO/aid-worker that offered support? (multiple choice possible)

- Local people
- Relatives or friends of yours
- Police/soldiers/border guards
- Public institutions (such as Red Cross, or others)
- Local humanitarian organizations
- International humanitarian organizations such as UNHCR, or others
- Mosques/ churches
- If other, please specify

A9. Did you experience detention after leaving Syria?

- Yes go to A9a
- No go to B1

A9a. For how long? Please specify how many HOURS?

Part B: International protection

Now we would like to ask you some questions on the protection of asylum seekers and refugees as well as on your daily life in Sweden.

B1. How do you feel in your neighborhood in Sweden?

- Safe go to B3
- Somewhat safe go to B3
- Somewhat unsafe go to B2
- Unsafe go to B2

B2. If you do not feel safe, why? (multiple choice possible)

- Racism / discrimination
- Problems with Swedish locals
- Theft
- Some bad individuals
- Refugee neighbourhoods are unsafe
- Sweden is not safe
- Threats of violence / verbal aussault
- Lack of proper shelter
- Fear of closing the shelter or camp
- Fear of being deported
- Fear of other ethnic / religious groups
- If other, please specify

B3. In Sweden, Have you ever been? (multiple choice possible)

- raided / searched
- insulted
- harassed
- beaten
- blackmailed
- extorted
- arrested / Detained
- evicted
- received departure order
- deported out of Turkey
- None of the above-mentioned
- exposed to another kind of violence (what kind?)

B4_S. Below you can find a list of issues related to the protection situation of refugees. For each one, please mark if it is a serious problem, a minor problem, or no problem at all for you and your family in Sweden.

	Serious problem	Minor problem	No problem	Not relevant
Access to labour market/ availability of jobs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to medical care	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to education	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to adequate housing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to residence permit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to legal aid	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to security forces or court case when you encounter problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protection against discrimination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protection against violence	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protection against exploitation in work place	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of safety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preconceptions and misconceptions about refugees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Protection from forced relocation, expulsion, detention	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Only three more sections!

Part C: Integration – language, employment, citizenship

Now we want to ask you some questions on languages that you speak and learn, your employment and citizenship.

C1. What level of the following languages do you have?

If you speak more than one "other language", enlist all of them in comments section using the above-mentioned scale.

	No proficiency	Basic communication skills/ working knowledge	Good command/ good working knowledge	Very good command	Excellent command/ highly proficient in spoken and written	Near-native / fluent
Swedish	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
English	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arabic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify in comment)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other:

C2. Are you currently learning Swedish?

- Yes go to C3
- No go to C4

C3. How are you learning the Swedish language?? (multiple choice possible)

- Daily life in the host country go to C6
- Language classes in the host country go to C6
- If another way, please specify.....go to C6

C4. Do you wish to learn Swedish?

- Yes go to C6
- No go to C5

C5. If you don't want to learn Swedish, please indicate why (multiple choice possible)

- I do not find it necessary
- It is too difficult
- If other, please specify

Now we would like to ask you some questions on your job.

C6. Have you ever had a paid job in Sweden, either as an employee or as self-employed ?

- Yes go to C7
- No go to C15

C7. How long did it take you to start working after your arrival in Sweden?

Months

C8. Are you currently working?

- Yes go to C10
- No go to C9

C9. If you are not working now, for how long were you being unemployed? go to C 15

Months

C10. What is your current job performed in Sweden?

- Unskilled worker (e.g. maid, waiter, kitchen help, agricultural worker, cleaner, babysitter)
- Skilled worker or craftsman (e.g. welder, machine operator, qualified bricklayer, tailor, nurse, operator of agricultural machinery, forester)
- Service employee or salesperson (hairdresser, beautician, cook)
- Office worker, a technician and other middle personnel (secretary, electrician)
- Specialist (lawyer, doctor, bookkeeper, lecturer, IT specialist, teacher, translator)
- Manager / supervisor / director
- If other, please specify

C11. In which sector is your current job performed in Sweden?

- Agriculture
- Manufacturing (industry and crafts)
- Retail/ wholesail trade
- Tourism
- Foodservice
- Construction and renovation services
- Household services
- Education and translation
- Health and social service
- IT /banking/ accounting / consulting/ marketing
- Other services, please specify

Other sector, please specify

C12. How did you find your current job?

- Through family or friends in Sweden
- Through NGO in Sweden
- Through official institution (e.g. Job center " Arbetsförmedlingen) in Sweden
- Through intermediaries
- If other way, please specify

C13. How many hours per week do you work currently?

C14. What level of Swedish is required for your current job?

- No proficiency
- Only basic communication skills
- Good command/ good working knowledge
- Very good command
- Excellent command/ highly proficient in spoken and written
- Near native/ fluent

C15. Have you attended any professional training in Sweden (excluding language classes)?

- Yes
- No

C16. Based on your experience, what are the difficulties as asylum seekers/refugees when looking for a job (multiple choice possible)

- Legal barriers to take up jobs officially
- Employers not willing to hire asylum seekers/ refugees
- Employers not willing to pay for SGK/ insurance
- Necessity to know Swedish language well
- Only simple and low paid jobs accessible for asylum seekers / refugees
- Lack of recognition of competences from home country
- No difficulties/ Not relevant
- If other, please specify

Now we would like to ask you some questions on your citizenship and your plans.

C17_S. What is your current legal status in Sweden?

- 1. Refugee status (with permanent residency through UNHCR)
- 2. Refugee status (with permanent residency through the applicable old law before 2016)
- 3. Refugee status (with temporary residency through the applicable new law after 2016)
- 4. Subsidiary Protection status (with permanent residency through the applicable law before 2016)
- 5. Subsidiary Protection Status(with temporary residency through the applicable law after 2016)
- 6. Family reunification based status (with permanent residency through the applicable old law after 2016)
- 7. Family reunification based status (temporary residency through the applicable new law after 2016)
- 8. a person otherwise in need of protection status for example because of natural disaster or armed conflicts (with temporary residency permit)

Other than that

C18. What is your attitude towards acquiring Swedish citizenship?

- I do not want to have it
- I would like to have it, but I do not think it is possible
- I would like to have it and I have already applied for it
- I would like to have it and I will apply for it in the future
- I already have it

C19. What are, according to you, the biggest obstacles in getting the host country citizenship? (multiple choice possible)

- Long and complicated legal procedure
- Hostility of the host country's government towards refugees
- Xenophobia of the host country society
- If other, please specify

C20. How much do you feel part of the Swedish society?

- Not at all
- Very little
- Somewhat
- Much

C21. Which statements below may express your considerations about returning to Syria?

- I never think of returning to Syria
- I may return in case the war in Syria ends and a good government is established
- I may return in case the war in Syria ends, even if there is not yet a good government
- I may return even if the war in Syria continues
- I do not have an idea, I do not know

C22. Do you want to go to any other country rather than Syria and Sweden for settlement?

- I never consider going
- If I find a chance, I will go
- If I cannot find a job in Sweden, I will go
- If I am given an opportunity for employment, I will go
- If other, please specify

C22a. Which other country do you want to move to?

Just two sections left!

Part D: Psycho-social health and discrimination

Now we would like to ask you some questions on your health and coping with difficult situations.

D1. In general, would you say your psychological health is

- Very poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Very good

D2. Have you experienced a very difficult situation, e.g. serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture?

- Yes go to D2a
- No go to D3

D2a. If yes please name these difficulties.....

D3. In your life, have you ever had any experience that was so frightening, horrible, or upsetting that, in the past month, you ...

	Yes	No
... have had nightmares about it or thought about it when you did not want to?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... tried hard not to think about it or went out of your way to avoid situations that reminded you of it?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... were constantly on guard, watchful, or easily startled?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
... felt numb or detached from others, activities, or your surroundings?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D4. In general, would you say...

	Not true at all	Rarely true	Sometimes true	Often true	True nearly all the time
D4a ... I am able to adapt when changes occur.	<input type="radio"/>				
D4b ... I tend to bounce back after illness, injury, or other hardships.	<input type="radio"/>				

D5. Have you ever experienced discrimination, been prevented from doing something, or been hassled or made to feel inferior in any of the following situations because of your race, ethnicity, religion, or colour?

	Never	Once	Several times	Many times
At school	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Getting hired or getting a job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
At work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
During getting housing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
During getting medical care	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
During getting services in a store or restaurant	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On the street or in a public setting	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From the police or in the courts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
From other authorities (e.g., Social Services, Migration office, Tax authority, National Insurance Agency)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because of Swedish language in your context outside home	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D6. To what extent here in Sweden do the following help you in coping with any difficult situation you are facing? Where "0" means "not relevant", "1" means not at all and "10" means very much

	Not at all 1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Very much 10	Not relevant 0
Family	<input type="radio"/>										
Friends	<input type="radio"/>										
Faith/ Religion/ Spirituality	<input type="radio"/>										
Work/ School	<input type="radio"/>										
Being out in Nature	<input type="radio"/>										
Other	<input type="radio"/>										
Please add to the list any important aspects that you find in Sweden.	<input type="radio"/>										

If other, please specify

Just few more demographic questions!

Parents' and Children's Rights and Integration

Statements in this section are about your attitude towards the Swedish values regarding gender equality, parental responsibility and child's rights in the Swedish law. To what extent do you agree with the following statement even if you do not have children at this time.

IN THE CASE OF DIVORCE AND ABSENT DISAGREEMENT REGARDING PARENTAL RIGHTS, THE SWEDISH SECULAR LEGAL AND JUDICIAL FAMILIAL SYSTEM STRONGLY PRE-ASSUMES THE FOLLOWING: JOINT EQUAL PARENTAL RESPONSIBILITY IN ALL IMPORTANT DECISIONS CONCERNING THE CHILD'S UPBRINGING, EDUCATION AND WELFARE, FINANCIAL MATTERS CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTERESTS OF THE CHILD.

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
1. The Swedish system fits me well in Sweden.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

IN THE CASE OF DIVORCE AND ABSENT DISAGREEMENT REGARDING PARENTAL RIGHTS, THE SYRIAN RELIGION-BASED LEGAL AND JUDICIAL FAMILIAL SYSTEM STRONGLY PRE-ASSUMES THE FOLLOWING:

THE FATHER'S SOLE GUARDIANSHIP IN MOST SUBSTANTIAL MATTERS CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTEREST OF THE MUSLIM CHILD.

THE MOTHER'S Custody UNTIL A CERTAIN AGE (13 GIRLS AND 15 BOYS) CONSTITUTES THE BEST INTEREST OF THE MUSLIM CHILD.

THE PARENTS' RELIGIOUS BACKGROUND PLAYS A CENTRAL ROLE IN RELATION TO PARENTS'- AND CHILD RIGHTS AFTER DIVORCE, WHICH MEANS DIFFERENT RULES MAY APPLY IF THE CHILD IS SYRIAN CHRISTIAN.

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
2. A. This system can work only in a Muslim country like Syria.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. B. This system fits me well in Syria.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
3. I am prepared to accept that a mother can have sole guardianship or custody if that is in the child's best interest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

When it is necessary to place the child under care, due to serious shortcomings in parental care:

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
4.A. I accept that the child is placed in the care of a suitable family relative in Sweden if that is in the child's best interest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4.B. I accept that the child is placed in the care of a suitable non- relative in Sweden if there is no suitable family relative and that is in the child's best interest.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How much would you like your children to integrate into Swedish society valuing gender equality e.g. as regards their right to develop as autonomous individuals, the right to have a boyfriend / girlfriend?

	Not At All 0	Very Little 1	Somewhat 2	Much 3	Completely 4
5.A. How much would you like it in the case of your sons?	<input type="radio"/>				
5.B. How much would you like it in the case of your daughters?	<input type="radio"/>				

To what extent do you agree with the following statements in relation to your children's integration into the Swedish society?

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
6.A. We have a plan to return to the country of origin	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.B. I do not care about the value base of gender equality in the Swedish society when it comes to my child's rights to choose a partner (boyfriend or girlfriend).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.C. I wish that my children will cherish the Syrian culture values.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.D. I wish that my children will cherish the Swedish culture values.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.E. I wish my children to have a good future in Sweden.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.F. Other reasons. Please specify:.....	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other reasons, please specify.....

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Completely disagree 0	Mostly disagree 1	Partly agree 2	Mostly agree 3	Completely agree 4
7. I am ready to make some compromises concerning my religious practices to better integrate into the Swedish society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In the Swedish public school system, teaching and education are non-confessional. Teaching about all the major religions is a part of the curriculum for all students. The Swedish system permits to date that faith communities operate religious schools, upon special public authorisation, for Muslim, Christian and Jewish followers. Religious or confessional elements are allowed in these educational contexts but not in the teaching, and students have the freedom to attend or not.

To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

	Agree Totally 1	Agree Partly 2	Reject Partly 3	Reject Totally 4	Neither agree nor reject/ I not know 5
8. Religious schools counteract integration	<input type="radio"/>				

Demographics

P1. What is your current relationship situation? (multiple choice possible)

- Married
- Divorced
- Engaged
- Widowed
- Single
- If other, please specify

P2. Do you have children?

- No go to P3
- Yes to P2a and P2b

P2a. If yes, how many are with you now?

P2b. And how many are living somewhere else?

P3. Which is Your or Your parents' background culture (culture of origin)? For example Syrian, Kurdish, Assyrian/Syriac, Chaldean, Turkoman, or other?

P4. Do you belong to a religion or religious denomination? If yes, which one?

- Catholic (Chaldean/Syrian/etc.)
- Druze
- Mandaean
- Muslim (Suni)
- Muslim (Shia)
- Orthodox (Syrian/ Assyrian/ etc.)
- Yazidi
- Do not belong to a denomination
- If other, please specify

P5. To which extent do you feel religious?

- Not at all
- Very little
- Somewhat
- Much

P6. What is the highest level of your education?

- Primary school
- Lower upper secondary school
- Highschool
- 2 years institution, -önlisans-associate degree
- Tertiary (University)
- PhD

P7. What is the subject area of your highest level of education?

- General programmes without any subject
- Education and pedagogy
- Humanities (e.g. linguistics, history, theology) and art
- Social sciences (e.g. sociology, psychology, anthropology)
- Economy, business and financial studies
- Law
- Life sciences (e.g. biology, botany, zoology, microbiology, physiology, biochemistry)
- Physical and environmental sciences
- Mathematics and computing
- Engineering and technology
- Manufacturing and processing
- Architecture and building
- Agriculture, forestry, fishery
- Veterinary
- Health and medicine
- Social services
- Services
- Media, culture, tourism
- Public administration
- Uniformed services
- Other, please specify

P8. What is the type of your current place of residence?

- Rural area
- Small town up to 20,000 people
- Medium town of more than 20,001 up to 100,000 people
- Big town of more than 100,001 up to 1,000,000
- Large city of more than 1,000,001 people

P9_T. What type of accommodation do you have?

- Rented single room
- Rented apartment
- Own apartment
- Rented house
- Own house
- Unfinished shelter
- Makeshift shelter
- Gecekondü house
- Collective shelter
- Other, please specify

Do you have any comments?

A5	من كان يحاول منعك من دخول السويد؟ 1. الشرطة 2. حرس الحدود 3. الجيش 4. خفر السواحل 5. فرونتكس 6. السكان المحليين 7. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد).....
A6	هل حاولت أي سلطات على طول المعابر الحدودية إعادتك إلى البلد الذي وصلت منه؟ 1. إذا كان جوابك نعم أذهب إلى A6a_s 2. إذا كان جوابك لا أذهب إلى A7
A6a_s	يرجى سرد أسماء هذه الدول 1..... 2..... 3..... 4..... 5..... 6.....

الآن، يرجى التفكير في الأيام والأسابيع الأولى بعد عبور الحدود السورية.	
A7	ما نوع الدعم الذي قدم لك؟ (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة) 1. مأوى (مكان للبقاء) 2. وسائل العيش (الطعام / الماء ، الملابس ، الخ ..) 3. الدعم اللوجستي للوصول إلى وجهتك مثل المخيم، والأقارب، أو في أي مكان آخر 4. المساعدة القانونية حول وضعك 5. المعلومات 6. شيء آخر (يرجى التحديد بإيجاز)..... 7. إذا لم يتم تقديم أي دعم أنتقل إلى A9 8. إذا لم يكن هناك حاجة للدعم أنتقل إلى A9
A8	بمجرد عبورك الحدود السورية من كان أول شخص ، أو مؤسسة منظمة غير حكومية موظف إغاثة قدم الدعم؟ (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة) 1. المواطنين المحليين 2. أقارب أو أصدقاء لك 3. الشرطة / الجنود / حرس الحدود 4. المؤسسات العامة مثلا (Göç İdaresi AFAD, Kızılay) , أو غيرها 5. المنظمات المحلية الإنسانية مثلا (İHH ، ASAM ، MÜDEM ، Deniz Feneri) 6. المنظمات الإنسانية الدولية مثل المفوضية السامية للأمم المتحدة لشؤون اللاجئين ، المنظمة الدولية للهجرة ، أو ياريبوزو دكتور 7. الكنائس المساجد 8. غير ذلك (يرجى تحديدها بإيجاز)
A9	هل واجهت الاعتقال بعد مغادرة سوريا؟ 1. إذا كان الجواب نعم أذهب إلى A9a 2. إذا كان الجواب لا أذهب إلى B1
A9a	مدة الاعتقال؟ 1. كم ساعة.....

الجزء ب: الحماية الدولية	
الآن نود أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة حول الحماية لطالبي اللجوء واللاجئين وعلى الحياة اليومية لك في السويد.	
B1	كيف تشعر في منطقتكم في السويد؟ 1. إذا كنت تشعر بالأمان اذهب إلى B3 2. إذا كنت تشعر إلى حد ما آمن اذهب إلى B3 3. إذا كنت تشعر إلى حد ما غير آمن اذهب إلى B2 4. إذا كنت تشعر غير آمن اذهب إلى B2

B2	إذا كنت لا تشعر بالأمان، لماذا؟ (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة)	1. العنصرية / التمييز	2. مشاكل مع السكان المحليين السويديين	3. سرقة
		4. بعض الأفراد السيئين	5. أحياء اللاجئين غير آمنة	6. السويد ليست آمنة
		7. التهديد بالعنف / الاعتداء اللفظي	8. عدم وجود المأوى المناسب	9. الخوف من إغلاق المأوى أو معسكر اللجوء
		10. الخوف من الترحيل	11. الخوف من المجموعات القومية أو الدينية الأخرى	
		12. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد بإيجاز).....		

B3	هل حدث و أنك تعرضت إلى إي من الحوادث التالية في السويد؟ (الاختيار المتعدد ممكن)	1. مداومة & تفتيش
		2. إهانة
		3. مضايقة
		4. الضرب
		5. الابتزاز
		6. الاستغلال
		7. الاعتقال والحبس
		8. الطرد
		9. تلقيت امر بالترحيل
		10. تم ترحيلك من السويد
		11. تعرضت إلى أي نوع من العنف في السويد (إذا كان الامر كذلك أي نوع).....
		12. لم أتعرض إلى أي شيء من المذكور أعلاه.

B4.T	فيما يلي يمكنك العثور على قائمة بنود بالمشاكل المتعلقة بوضع حماية اللاجئين. يرجى وضع علامة لكل بند , إذا كانت مشكلة خطيرة، او مشكلة بسيطة، أو ليست مشكلة على الإطلاق بالنسبة لك او غير ذات صلة لك ولعائلتك في السويد؟	مشكلة خطيرة	مشكلة بسيطة	ليست مشكلة على الإطلاق	غير ذات صلة
1.	الوصول إلى سوق العمل & توفر فرص العمل	1	2	3	0
2.	الوصول على الرعاية الطبية	1	2	3	0
3.	الحصول على التعليم	1	2	3	0
4.	الحصول على السكن الملائم	1	2	3	0
5.	الوصول أو إمكانية الحصول على كرت الإقامة	1	2	3	0
6.	الوصول للمساعدة القانونية	1	2	3	0
7.	إمكانية الوصول إلى القوى الأمنية أو القضاء في حال مواجهة مشاكل	1	2	3	0
8.	حماية ضد التمييز	1	2	3	0
9.	حماية ضد العنف	1	2	3	0
10.	حماية ضد الاستغلال في مكان العمل	1	2	3	0
11.	نقص الأمان	1	2	3	0
12.	مفاهيم مسبقة ومفاهيم خاطئة حول اللاجئين	1	2	3	0
13.	الحماية من الترحيل القسري والطرده والاحتجاز	1	2	3	0

الجزء ج : الإندماج - اللغة ، التوظيف ، الجنسية

الآن نريد أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة عن كل اللغات التي تعلمها وتتعلمها

C1							ما هو مستواك في اللغات التالية	
لا أتقان على الإطلاق	مهارات أساسية فقط للتواصل و معرفة للعمل	تمكن جيد ومعرفة جيدة للعمل	تمكن جيد جداً	تمكن ممتاز و إتقان ممتازة بالكتابة و التحدث	تمكن كأنها لغتك الام	0	1	
1. اللغة السويدية	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
2. اللغة الإنجليزية	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
3. اللغة العربية	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
4. لغة أخرى (من فضلك حدد).....	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
5. لغة أخرى (من فضلك حدد).....	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
6. لغة أخرى (من فضلك حدد).....	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	
C2	هل تتعلم حالياً اللغة السويدية؟						1. إذا كان جوابك ب نعم انتقل إلى C3 2. إذا كان جوابك ب لا انتقل إلى C4	
C3	كيف تتعلم اللغة السويدية؟ (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة)						1. من خلال الحياة اليومية في السويد. إذهب إلى C6 2. من خلال دورات و فصول اللغة في السويد. إذهب إلى C6 3. طرق أخرى (يرجى التحديد بإيجاز) إذهب إلى C6	
C4	هل ترغب في تعلم اللغة السويدية؟						1. إذا كان جوابك ب نعم اذهب إلى C6 2. إذا كان جوابك ب لا اذهب إلى C5	
C5	إذا كنت لا ترغب في تعلم اللغة السويدية، يرجى توضيح السبب (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة)						1. لا أجد ذلك ضرورياً 2. إنه صعب للغاية 3. أسباب أخرى (يرجى التحديد)	

الآن نود أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة عن عملك.	
C6	هل سبق لك أن حصلت على وظيفة مدفوعة الأجر في السويد، سواء كموظف أو كعامل لحسابك الخاص؟
C7	كم من الوقت استغرقتك لبدء العمل بعد وصولك إلى السويد؟
C8	هل تعمل حالياً؟
C9	إذا كنت لا تعمل الآن، منذ متى و انت عاطل عن العمل؟
C10	ما هي وظيفتك الحالية التي تؤديها في السويد؟
	1. العمالة التي لا تتطلب المهارة (مثل خادمة ، النادل ، مساعدة المطبخ ، عامل غير ماهر ، عامل زراعي ، نظافة ، جليسة أطفال) 2. عامل ماهر أو حرفي (على سبيل المثال ، عامل لحام ، مشغل ماكينة ، خبيرة بناء مؤهلة ، خياط ، ممرض ، مشغل للآلات الزراعية ، حراجي) 3. موظف خدمة أو مندوب مبيعات (مصفف شعر ، تجميل ، طبخ) 4. موظف مكتب ، فني وموظفين متوسطين آخرين (سكرتير ، كهربائي) 5. أخصائي (محامي ، طبيب ، محاسب ، محاضر ، متخصص في تكنولوجيا المعلومات ، معلم ، مترجم) 6. مدير مشرف 7. غير ذلك (يرجى التوضيح).....

C11	في أي قطاع من القطاعات التالية يكون عملك الحالي في السويد؟	1. الزراعة 2. التصنيع (الصناعة والحرف اليدوية) 3. تجارة التجزئة / تجارة الجملة 4. السياحة 5. الخدمات الغذائية 6. خدمات البناء والتجديد 7. الخدمات المنزلية 8. التعليم والترجمة 9. الصحة والخدمات الاجتماعية 10. تكنولوجيا المعلومات المصرفية / المحاسبة استشارات / تسويق 11. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد)
C12	كيف وجدت وظيفتك الحالية في السويد؟	1. من خلال العائلة أو الأصدقاء في السويد. 2. من خلال المنظمات غير الحكومية في السويد. 3. من خلال مؤسسة رسمية (على سبيل المثال مكتب العمل ، مكتب الأجانب) في السويد 4. من خلال الوسطاء 5. طريقة أخرى (كيف؟)
C13	كم ساعة في الاسبوع تعمل حالياً؟	عدد الساعات اسبوعياً
C14	ما هو مستوى اللغة السويدية المطلوب لعملك الحالي؟	0. لا حاجة للإتقان 1. مهارات الاتصال الأساسية فقط 2. مهارات جيدة للتواصل & معرفة جيدة فيما يخص العمل 3. مهارات لغوية جيدة جداً 4. تمكن ممتاز & مهارات ممتازة بالكتابة و التحدث 5. لساني طليق تقريبا كأنها اللغة الام
C15	هل حضرت أي تدريب مهني في السويد (بغض النظر عن دروس اللغة)؟	1. نعم 2. لا
C16	بناء على خبرتك، ما هي الصعوبات التي تواجه طالبي اللجوء و اللاجئين عند البحث عن وظيفة في السويد (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة)	1. حاجز قانوني للحصول على الوظائف بشكل رسمي 2. أرباب العمل غير راغبين في توظيف او استئجار طالبي اللجوء / اللاجئين 3. ضرورة معرفة اللغة السويدية جيداً 4. فقط وظائف بسيطة ومنخفضة الأجر يمكن الوصول إليها لطالبي اللجوء / اللاجئين. 5. عدم الاعتراف بالاختصاصات من البلد الأم 6. غير ذلك (ماذا؟)

الآن نود أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة عن جنسيتك وخطتك	
C17_T	ما هي الصفة او الوضع القانوني لأقامتك في السويد؟
1.	صفة لجوء (مع إقامة دائمة عن طريق مفوضية الامم المتحدة للاجئين)
2.	صفة لجوء (مع إقامة دائمة بناء على القانون القديم المطبقة قبل 2016)
3.	صفة لجوء (مع إقامة مؤقتة بناء على القانون المؤقت المطبقة منذ 2016)
4.	صفة الحماية البديلة (مع إقامة دائمة بناء على القانون القديم المطبقة قبل 2016)
5.	صفة الحماية البديلة (مع إقامة مؤقتة بناء على القانون المؤقت المطبقة منذ 2016)
6.	صفة قانونية مبنية على لم شمل الاسرة (مع إقامة دائمة بناء على القانون القديم المطبقة قبل 2016)
7.	صفة قانونية مبنية على لم شمل الاسرة (مع إقامة مؤقتة بناء على القانون المؤقت المطبقة منذ 2016)
8.	صفة الحماية لشخص بحاجة للحماية في حالات معين كالاجئين بسبب الكوارث البيئية او النزاعات المسلحة اذا قدموا لجوء قبل 24 نوفمبر 2015 (مع إقامة مؤقتة)
9.	غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد بايجاز)

C18	فما هو موقفك من إمكانية الحصول على الجنسية السويدية؟ 1. لا أرغب في الحصول عليها 2. أود الحصول عليها ، لكنني لا أعتقد أنه ممكن 3. أود الحصول عليها وقد تقدمت بالفعل بطلبها 4. أود الحصول عليه وسأقدم الطلب في المستقبل 5. أنا حصلت عليها مسبقاً
C19	ما هي ، وفقاً لك ، أكبر العقبات في الحصول على الجنسية السويدية؟ (الاختيارات المتعددة ممكنة) 1. إجراءات قانونية طويلة ومعقدة 2. عداة حكومة البلد المضيقة تجاه اللاجئين 3. كراهية الأجانب في مجتمع البلد المضيف 4. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد بإيجاز)
C20	إلى أي مدى تشعر بأنك جزء من المجتمع السويدي؟ 1. لا اشعر على الإطلاق 2. القليل جداً 3. إلى حد ما 4. كثيراً
C21	إي من العبارات أدناه قد تعبر عن أفكارك حول العودة إلى سوريا؟ 1. أنا أبداً لا أفكر في العودة إلى سوريا 2. قد أعود في حالة انتهاء الحرب في سوريا وإنشاء حكومة جيدة 3. قد أعود في حال انتهاء الحرب في سوريا، حتى لو لم تنشأ حكومة جيدة بعد 4. قد أعود حتى لو استمرت الحرب في سوريا 5. ليس لدي فكرة، وأنا لا أعرف
C22	هل تريد الذهاب إلى أي بلد آخر بدلاً من سوريا والسويد من أجل الاستيطان؟ 1. أنا لا أفكر في الذهاب 2. إذا وجدت فرصة، سأذهب. 3. إذا لم أتمكن من العثور على وظيفة في السويد ، فسأذهب. 4. إذا أتاحت لي فرصة للتوظيف ، فسأذهب. 5. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد بإيجاز)
C22a	إلى أي بلد تريد أنت تذهب ؟ C22a إذا كانت الجواب نعم أنتقل إلى C22a انتقل إلى C22a أنتقل إلى C22a أنتقل إلى

الجزء د: الصحة النفسية والاجتماعية والتميز

الآن نود أن نسألك بعض الأسئلة عن صحتك والتعامل مع المواقف الصعبة

	غير جيدة على الإطلاق	غير جيدة	وسط	جيدة	جيدة جداً
D1	1	2	3	4	5
D2	هل واجهت وضعاً صعباً للغاية ، على سبيل المثال؟ حادث خطير ، كارثة طبيعية ، اغتصاب ، حرب ، سوء معاملة ، تعذيب؟				
D2a	إذا كانت الإجابة بنعم ، يرجى ذكر هذه الصعوبات				

D3	في حياتك ، هل واجهت أي تجربة كانت مخيفة أو فظيعة أو مزعجة ، و أدى ذلك انك في الشهر الماضي ، كنت :
1.	لديك كوابيس حول ذلك أو فكرت في ذلك عندما كنت لا تريد؟
2.	حاولت جاهداً عدم التفكير في ذلك أو متابعة طريقك لتجنب المواقف التي تذكرك بالأمر؟
3.	دائمًا في حالة دهشة أو ترقب أو تأهب بسهولة؟
4.	شعرت بخدر أو انفصال عن الآخرين ، أو الأنشطة التي تدور حولك ، أو محيطك؟

بشكل عام هل تستطيع ان تقول أنك						هذا ليس صحيحا على الاطلاق	نادرا صحيح	أحيانا صحيح	غالباً صحيح	دائماً صحيح
D4a	قادر على التكيف عند حدوث التغييرات	1	2	3	4	5				
D4b	أميل إلى استعادة التوازن بعد المرض أو الإصابة، أو غيرها من الصعوبات.	1	2	3	4	5				

D5		هل سبق لك أن تعرضت للتمييز أو تم منعك من القيام بشيء ما أو تم ازعاجك أو جعلك تشعر بالدونية في أي من الحالات التالية بسبب أو قوميتك أو جنسيتك أو دينك ؟	لا ابدا	مرة واحدة	عدة مرات	مرات كثيرة
1	في المدرسة	0	1	2	3	
2	أثناء الحصول على عمل او التوظيف	0	1	2	3	
3	في العمل	0	1	2	3	
4	أثناء الحصول على سكن	0	1	2	3	
5	أثناء الحصول على عناية صحية و طبية	0	1	2	3	
6	أثناء الحصول على خدمات في مخزن او مطعم	0	1	2	3	
7	في الشارع و الأماكن العامة	0	1	2	3	
8	من الشرطة و المحاكم	0	1	2	3	
9	من السلطات الأخرى (على سبيل المثال ، الخدمات الاجتماعية ، مكتب الهجرة ، مصلحة الضرائب ، وكالة التأمين الوطنية)	0	1	2	3	

D6											إلى أي مدى ساعدك هنا في السويد ما يلي في مواجهة أي موقف صعب واجهته؟	ليس على الاطلاق	كثير جدا	غير ذي صلة
1	العائلة	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		
2	الأصدقاء	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		
3	الدين و الروحانية و الايمان	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		
4	العمل و المدرسة	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		
5	ان تكون في الطبيعة (في الغابة أو قرب البحر او في الحديقة العامة)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		
من فضلك أضع أي موضوع أو شيء مهم ساعدك في السويد في مواجهة أي موقف صعب واجهته														
6	أمور أخرى (اشرح من فضلك).....	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0		

حقوق الطفل و مسؤولية الأبوين (الحضانة و الولاية) و الأندماج

تتعلق الأسئلة و التصريحات في هذه القسم بموقفك من القيم السويدية فيما يتعلق بالمساواة بين الجنسين ، و مسؤولية الأبوين و حقوق الطفل في القانون السويدي. من فضلك أجب إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريحات الآتية في هذه القسم حتى لو لم يكن لديك أطفال حالياً.

أ. في حالة الطلاق الذي لا يوجد فيه نزاع بشأن حقوق الوالدين (الحضانة و الولاية) ، فإن النظام القضائي والقانوني السويدي (العلماني) للأسرة يفترض بقوة ما يلي إن مصلحة الطفل الفضلى هي ان الوالدين مسؤولين مسؤولية مشتركة بشكل متساوي في جميع القرارات المهمة المتعلقة بتربية الطفل وتعليمه ورفاهه.

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريح التالي	لا اوافق بشكل كامل	لا اوافق بشكل عموماً	لا اوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
1. النظام السويدي القانوني و القضائي للأسرة يناسبني جيداً في السويد	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

ب. في حالة الطلاق الذي لا يوجد فيه نزاع بشأن حقوق الوالدين ، فإن النظام القانوني والقضائي السوري (القائم على الدين) للأسرة يفترض بقوة ما يلي:

ان المصلحة الفضلى للطفل المسلم هي في حصر الولاية للأب في معظم الأمور الجوهرية.

إن المصلحة الفضلى للطفل المسلم هي في حضانة الأم حتى عمر معين (13 للطفل و 15 للطفلة).

تلعب الخلفية الدينية للوالدين دوراً رئيسياً فيما يتعلق بمسؤولية الوالدين و حقوق الطفل بعد الطلاق، مما يعني إمكانية تطبيق قواعد مختلفة إذا كان الطفل مسيحياً سورياً.

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريح التالي	لا اوافق بشكل كامل	لا اوافق بشكل عموماً	لا اوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
2.أ هذا النظام القانوني و القضائي للأسرة ممكن ان يطبق فقط في دولة مسلمة كسوريا	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
2.ب هذا النظام القانوني و القضائي للأسرة يناسبني جيداً في سوريا	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريح التالي	لا اوافق بشكل كامل	لا اوافق بشكل عموماً	لا اوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
3. أنا مستعد لقبول أن تكون الولاية و الحضانة حصرياً للام إذا كان ذلك في مصلحة الطفل الفضلى	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريح التالي	لا اوافق بشكل كامل	لا اوافق بشكل عموماً	لا اوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
إذا كان لابد من وضع الطفل تحت الرعاية بسبب حالة القصور الخطير في بيت الوالدين	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
4.أ. فأني اوافق أن يوضع الطفل تحت رعاية اسرة مناسبة من الأقارب في السويد.	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
4.ب. فأني اوافق ان يوضع الطفل تحت رعاية اسرة مناسبة من غير الأقارب إذا لم يوجد اسرة مناسبة من الاقارب في السويد.	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

إلى أي مدى ترغب أن يندمج أطفالك في المجتمع السويدي الذي يقدر المساواة بين الجنسين مثلاً فيما يتعلق بحقهم في التطور كأفراد مستقلين والحق في اختيار صديق أو صديقة (Pojkvän)(flickvän)	لا على الإطلاق	قليل جداً	إلى حد ما	كثيراً	بشكل كامل
5.أ. إلى أي مدى ترغب بذلك لأبنائك الذكور	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4
5.ب. إلى أي مدى ترغب بذلك لبنتك الإناث	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريحات التالية المتعلقة باندماج أطفالك في المجتمع السويدي؟	لاوافق بشكل كامل	لاوافق بشكل عام	أوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
6. ا. لدينا خطة للعودة إلى بلد الاصل	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.ب- لا أهتم بقيم المساواة بين الجنسين في المجتمع السويدي عندما يتعلق الأمر بحق الأطفال الحصول على صديق أو صديقة (Pojkvän) flickvän)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.ت. أتمنى أن يعتز أولادي بقيم الثقافة السورية	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.ج. أتمنى أن يعتز أولادي بقيم الثقافة السويدية	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6.ح. أتمنى أن يحصل أطفالي على تعليم جيد ومستقبل في السويد	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>
6. ذ. أسباب أخرى. رجاء حدد.....	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

إلى أي مدى تتفق مع التصريح التالي	لاوافق بشكل كامل	لاوافق بشكل عام	أوافق بشكل جزئي	أوافق عموماً	أوافق بشكل كامل
7. أنا مستعد لتقديم بعض التنازلات فيما يتعلق بالممارسات الدينية الخاصة بي من أجل الاندماج بشكل أفضل في المجتمع السويدي	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>

في نظام المدارس الحكومية السويدية ، التعليم و التدريس غير ديني أو طائفي. يعد التدريس عن جميع الديانات الرئيسية جزءاً من المنهج لجميع الطلاب. كما و يسمح النظام السويدي للمجتمعات الدينية حتى الآن بتشغيل مدارس دينية ، بناءً على إذن خاص من السلطات العام ، للتابعين المسلمين والمسيحيين واليهود.					
في هذه المدارس الخاصة الدينية يسمح بوجود العناصر الدينية أو الطائفية في السياقات التعليمية ولكن ليس في التدريس ، ويتمتع الطلاب بحرية الحضور أو لا					
إلى أي مدى توافق مع التصريح التالي	أوافق بشكل كامل	أوافق بشكل جزئي	أرفض بشكل جزئي	أرفض بشكل كامل	لست موافقا أو رافضاً إلا أعلم
8. المدارس الدينية تتعارض مع الاندماج	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>

التركيبة السكانية	
P1.	ما هو وضعك العائلي الحالي؟ (الاجوبة المتعددة ممكنة) 1. متزوجة 2. مطلقة 3. مخطوبة 4. أرمل 5. عازبة 6. غير ذلك (من فضلك أشرح).....
P2.	هل لديك أطفال؟ 1. إذا كان الجواب نعم انتقل إلى P2a و P2b 2. إلى كان الجواب لا أنتقل إلى P3
P2A	فكم عدد اطفالك الموجودين معك الآن
P2B	وكم عدد اطفالك الذين يعيشون في مكان آخر
P3	ما هي ثقافتك أو ثقافة والديك (ثقافة المنشأ) ؟ على سبيل المثال سورية ، او عربية او الكرديّة او الأشوريّة /أو السريانيّة ، أو الكلدانيّة ، أو غير ذلك (من فضلك حدد).....

P4. هل تنتمي إلى دين أو طائفة دينية؟ إذا كان الجواب نعم أي واحد؟	
1	كاثوليك (كلداني سرياني..الخ)
2	درزي
3	مندائي
4	مسلم شيعة
5	مسلم سني
6	أرثوذكس (سرياني آشوري...الخ
7	يزيدي
8	غير ذلك
9	لا أنتمي إلى أي دين

P6. إلى أي مدى تشعر أنك متدين؟	
1	لا لست متدين على الإطلاق
2	متدين قليلا جدا
3	متدين إلى حد ما
4	الكثير

P7. ما هو أعلى مستوى تعليمي وصلت له؟	
1	المدرسة الابتدائية
2	المدرسة الاعدادية
3	المدرسة الثانوية (البكالوريا)
4	التعليم العالي (جامعة)
5	شهادة معهد (مدة سنتان)
6	الدكتوراه
7	لا شيء من المذكور سابقا (يرجى التوضيح).....

P8. ما هو مجال التخصص في أعلى مستوى تعليمي لك؟	
1.	برامج عامة دون أي مجال موضوعي
2.	التعليم والتربية
3.	العلوم الإنسانية (مثل اللغويات والتاريخ واللاهوت) والفن
4.	العلوم الاجتماعية (مثل علم الاجتماع وعلم النفس والأنثروبولوجيا)
5.	الاقتصاد والأعمال والدراسات المالية
6.	القانون
7.	علوم الحياة (مثل علم الأحياء ، علم النبات ، علم الحيوان ، علم الأحياء الدقيقة ، علم وظائف الأعضاء ، الكيمياء الحيوية)
8.	العلوم الفيزيائية والبيئية
9.	الرياضيات والحوسبة
10.	الهندسة والتكنولوجيا
11.	التصنيع والتجهيز
12.	العمارة والبناء
13.	الزراعة والغابات ومصايد الأسماك
14.	البيطري
15.	الصحة والطب
16.	الخدمات الاجتماعية
17.	الخدمات
18.	الإعلام والثقافة والسياحة
19.	الإدارة العامة
20.	الخدمات المنتظمة
21.	أخرى (يرجى التحديد).....

P9. ما هو نوع مكان إقامتك الحالي؟	
1.	منطقة ريفية
2.	بلدة صغيرة يصل عدد سكانها إلى 20.000 شخص
3.	بلدة متوسطة عدد سكانها بين 20.001 و 100.000 شخص
4.	مدينة كبيرة يصل عدد بين 100.001 و 1.000.000 شخص.
5.	مدينة كبيرة جدا عدد سكانها أكثر من 1.000.000 شخص.

P10.T. ما هو نوع السكن؟	
1.	غرفة واحدة مستأجرة
2.	شقة مستأجرة
3.	تملك شقة
4.	منزل ارضي مستأجر (بيت عربي)
5.	تملك منزل ارضي (بيت عربي)
6.	مأوى غير مكتمل
7.	مأوى مؤقت يتم تبديله بين اللاجئين

8 . بيت مشتمل على عدة غرف (غيجيكوندو)

9. مأوى جماعي & مخيم لاجئين

10. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد)

كان هذا هو السؤال الأخير. شكرا لك على وقتك

التعليقات.....
.....

تاريخ تعبئة الاستبيان اليوم _____ الشهر _____ السنة 20__

وقت بدأ المقابلة..... وقت أنتهاء المقابلة.....

من فضلك أشر إلى مكان تعبئة الاستبيان (مدينة أو قرية).....

رقم الشخص الذي يجري المقابلة.....